

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D2.5

Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs
against ethical and legal
standards

September 2022

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PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab.	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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Authors	Francesca Morpurgo, Valeria Cesaroni, Luigi Briguglio (CEL), Carmela Occhipinti (CEL), Emanuela Tangari (CEL), Sergi Vazquez Maymir (VUB)
Contributors	VUB
Reviewers	VUB, IR-HSCSP

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCC	Complex Chronic Conditions
CoBraD	Complex Brain Diseases
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
H2020	Horizon 2020
IRB	Institutional Review Board
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
Mx	Month x
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
No.	Number
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	PUC Organization
PUC	Pilot Use Case
RWD	Real-World Data
TBD	To Be Done
ToC	Table of Contents
UAT	User Acceptance Test
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

MES-CoBraD will develop 4 pilot use cases (“PUCs”) each one devoted to a different layer of the project and of the *to-be platform*. The first two pilot use cases will respectively be about the gathering and storage of real-world data (“RWD”) from the patients of the hospitals participating in the research (PUC1) and about the analysis of those datasets with the aid of advanced analytics tools, between which we include also machine learning (“ML”) and artificial intelligence (“AI”) algorithms (PUC2). The 3rd and 4th pilots (PUC3 and PUC4) will instead be devoted to testing (with the help of the knowledge gathered in the first two PUCs) drugs and therapies on patients and to the development of the final version of the MES-CoBraD platform, which includes an expert system for the diagnosis and care of complex brain diseases.

The objective of this deliverable is the ethical and legal assessment of the MES-CoBraD PUCs to support the project’s pilot partners during execution of their PUCs. Since at M18 only the first two pilots are in a sufficient advanced phase of development, here the focus is on PUC1 and PUC2, keeping in mind that some issues, like the ethical treatment of the patients or the use of AI in healthcare, will continue to be present in all the project and in particular in PUC3 and PUC4, so even though here we will not specifically evaluate PUC3 and PUC4, we lay the basis for their evaluation, which will be done in deliverable D2.8 in M24.

The legal and ethical assessments was carried out following a methodology customised on the project scope and objectives and based on the ethical requirements that – according to the ethical framework defined in D2.1 and D2.3 – the PUCs will have to respect (section 3.1).

The assessment process is described in section 3.2 and takes into account each requirement set up in section 3.1 :

- First of all, the available project documentation (the released deliverables mainly, but also further project documentation) was checked to assess if it adhered to the requirements (section 4 for the PUC1 and section 5 for the PUC2) and if possible mitigation actions are needed.
- Then, to gather the partners’ (both clinical and technical) experience as well as their opinions, they were asked to answer a questionnaire that was built around the same ethics requirements against which we performed the desktop assessment (the questions that we asked can be seen in Annex I). We discussed the questionnaire answers (section 6) and we confronted them against the results of the desktop assessment.
- In parallel, the data protection assessment of the PUC1 and PUC2 was carried out and reported in a specific section (section 8), which – moving from what has been thoroughly illustrated in D2.2 (data management plan) and D2.3 (ethical and legal framework) - checks whether the legal requirements have been satisfied. Particular attention is dedicated to the question of anonymisation and pseudonymisation of personal data and to the cybersecurity plan.
- Finally, as detailed in the document conclusion section, the assessment results were summarised, highlighting the elements we spotted and suggesting possible lines of action / of mitigation.

As a general comment, the ethics and legal requirements have been respected, with some areas of improvement that lie mostly in two fields:

- The meaning of the word “respect” that should be extended to include also areas not strictly connected to the consent but that should include showing empathy, listening to patients, letting them participate actively gathering their feedback both on the research approach and outcomes and on how they felt during their participation
- The consideration of the AI as some sort of sophisticated tool rather than as an “actor” who steps in the diagnostic process, an attitude that brings with it several consequences, like the questions

on autonomy and responsibility, that are at the moment under-represented (because they are not perceived as a problem). We argue that one of the reasons of this attitude lies in the fact that the platform is still not completely mature, but we think that from an ethical point of view is something that deserves to be furtherly explored, also with dedicated workshops and focus groups with partners and working on it in the Ethics, Policy and Society Work Group (WP4).

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The present deliverable is aimed at assessing the MES-CoBraD Pilot Use Cases (from now on: “PUCs”) from an ethical and normative perspective. The document will first outline the method applied for the assessment, the ethics requirements against which the assessment will be done, the assessment process and finally the assessment outcomes. Since MES-CoBraD research will involve human beings, also fragile and vulnerable ones, an ethical and data protection evaluation is of the utmost importance, especially if made with an open-minded attitude, where the outcomes of the assessment are taken as opportunities to change route and apply safeguards if something is not completely adherent to the ethics and legal requirements. Considering that the processing of personal data is at the core of the activities performed in both PUCs, the legal evaluation will pay close attention to how partners deal with data protection obligations.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

After a brief introduction in the current section 1 and a recap of the project PUCs in section 2, the document will describe the assessment methodology in section 3.

Then, after outlining the ethics requirements, the document will check their adoption both through a questionnaire (“self-assessment analysis” in section 6) and examining the available documentation (“desktop analysis” i.e. analysis based on available documentation and/or literature, in sections 4 and 5).

The document will then make a comparison between the self-assessment outcomes and the information gathered through the desktop analysis in section 7, to verify their alignment.

Since the normative framework and recommendations has been introduced in the D2.2 and D2.3 deliverables, section 8 will summarize and present how the same has been implemented by the partners in view of the PUCs.

Conclusions highlighting possible mitigation actions based on the findings of the assessment will be finally drawn in section 9.

1.3 RELATION TO OTHER DELIVERABLES/WPS/TASKS

This deliverable is in strict relation to all the WP2 deliverables and in particular to the D2.1 (where the ethical requirements are first outlined) and to the D2.3 (where an ethical and legal framework is defined). The D2.6 deliverable on the helpdesk (the v2 of the D2.1) also contains many areas that overlap and intersect with the present deliverable.

This deliverable is also based on the WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8 presently released deliverables dedicated to the PUCs, in particular on:

- D5.1 - Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security (PUC2 - Data gathering);
- D5.2- Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security - final (PUC2 - Data gathering);
- D6.1 - Advanced analytics prototype (PUC2 - Data analysis);
- D7.1 - System requirement and architecture (PUC2 - system architecture);
- D8.2 - MES-CoBraD validation framework (PUC1 - Real World Data acquisition);
- D8.3, D8.4 - Participant recruitment, pre-existing RWD access, Prospective RWD acquisition and secure storage (PUC1 - Real World Data acquisition).

2 THE MES-COBRA D PUCS

2.1 THE GENERAL IDEA BEHIND THE PUCS

MES-CoBraD is a complex project in which the latest findings of the medical sciences converge with the most advanced developments in analytical models to build an expert system that can be of support in the diagnosis and care of complex brain diseases (CoBraD).

For this reason, when fully operational, the system will be based on four different layers, each one representing a necessary element of the entire system. During the project these layers are represented by the four “pilot use cases” (PUCS) that are an exemplification of what the MES-CoBraD platform will be (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The four MES-CoBraD Pilot Use Cases (PUCs)

The pilots represent a preliminary glimpse of what the MES-CoBraD system will become when it will be effectively deployed and used in health care systems at scale. In short, the PUCs are designed to evaluate the impacts (in terms of scientific progress and social benefits) that the project could have on patients, caregivers, medical professionals, healthcare systems, and, by extension, society. The PUCs are coordinated through one or more Work Packages, so there isn't a single document containing all that is relevant for instance, to the PUC1, but the PUC1 emerges from the collation of multiple contributions and deliverables.

As we can read in the D1.2 section 3 deliverable, “The PUCs are coordinated primarily through three scientifically oriented WPs (i.e., WP3, WP4 and WP8), with WP3 establishing the infrastructure of Pilot RWD collection, WP4 organising and overseeing the processes for testing scientific hypotheses, and WP8 implementing the operations for Real-World Data (RWD) collection. These WPs are supported by technological packages of establishing a multidisciplinary database (WP5) and advanced analytics modules (WP6), which are combined into a Platform (WP7), and abide to legal and ethical principles (WP2).”

To achieve their aim, the PUCs contain a methodology for enrolling patients and acquiring real-world data, a methodology for the de-personalization and the storage of datasets, a machine learning module to analyze them, a user interface to allow researchers and clinicians to use the system, and to comprehensively integrate new knowledge to consolidate an expert system for the diagnosis and management of CoBraD.

The interesting aspect of this approach is that it allows studying “in vitro” the possible consequences, negative and positive, of introducing such a system into the national healthcare policies of the participating countries. Being an experiment, the numbers are not what they could be if the system was used at scale, but are nonetheless sufficient to evaluate the methodology and the approach, both from

an ethical and a scientific point of view.

Each PUC is intertwined with the other ones but at the same time is in some way autonomous and, due to its objectives and internal structure, presents not only medical and social opportunities, but also ethical and legal challenges to which it is important to pay attention.

Following, there is a detailed description of each PUC and its specific scientific objectives.

2.1.1 PUC1

MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol

Objective	<i>Use of Real-World Data to advance research on the management of complex chronic conditions and deep-phenotyping of CoBraD</i>
Status	<div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p><i>The acquisition protocol has been produced, keeping carefully in mind the personal data management, the patients' privacy and the overall involved clinics' data management policies.</i></p> <p><i>The data lake that will host all the RWD has been setup and is ready to be used. Moreover, an edge module, in charge of local data acquisition and depersonalization, has been designed and implemented according to a plugin-based architecture.</i></p> <p><i>The next steps are now the implementation of the actual data collection plugins from the heterogeneous data sources. Being a constant pursuit of implementing the MES-CoBraD protocol and analyzing data in-house for phenotyping CoBraD, the PUC1 will extend till the end of the project.</i></p>

This PUC establishes a new clinical protocol for the acquisition and use of multidisciplinary RWD between different institutions and between different types of Complex Chronic Conditions (CCC). In proposing this protocol, this PUC is representative of the multidisciplinary and multisource approach implemented by the project. The main goal of this PUC is to improve clinical outcomes by acquiring and integrating several RWDs. This PUC goes beyond the current literature concerning the diagnosis and assessment of persons with CoBraD, which focuses more on the isolated assessment of a single syndrome, while neglecting multidisciplinary analysis and comorbidities between different factors and syndromes.

To achieve this, a multisource diagnosis protocol (Figure 2) was designed based on the integration of different RWD modalities and their metadata, aiming to enable a deep-phenotyping of people with Non-Communicable Disease (NCD), epilepsy and sleep disorders, thus assessing comorbidities and addressing challenges of underdiagnosis, misdiagnosis, suboptimal diagnosis, and delay in diagnosis. For a more extensive description of the PUC1 and of the kind of RWD that are gathered through the protocol that has been specifically designed, please refer to the deliverable D3.2. History of the patient is gathered and taken into account, both through questionnaires and through physical and clinical examination.

Figure 2: Multisource Diagnosis Protocol

2.1.2 PUC2

MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication

Objective

Advanced Analytics and Artificial Intelligence on optimized diagnostic and therapeutic algorithms in CoBraD.

The Query Builder component, that builds on the database of RWD, supporting the comprehensive multidisciplinary analyses of big and interrelated data, is developed. The component is tested locally and shortly it will also be deployed on the integrated environment. It is also tested the connection with the implemented instance of project's DataLake.

Status

The Data Analytics & Visualisation components cope with a) the presentation of RWD acquired through EEG/PSG or MRI or Actigraphy data-files, and in parallel the provision of a toolset for further visual analysis (mostly focused on timeseries analysis), b) the support of Hypothesis testing and finally c) the visualisation of analyses results and the creation of the respective reports.

Up until now 15 methods for the visual analyses of different sources, and 19 tests (with several sub-methods) for the hypothesis testing have been implemented. All analyses include the visualisation of results and the creation of inclusive reports. Additionally, all implementations have been tested with sample data, acquired from our scientific partners.

PUC2 will focus on analysing RWD acquired as per MES-CoBraD Assessment Protocol in PUC1. The PUC2 will apply machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms (both supervised and unsupervised) for a more accurate phenotyping of CoBraD and to implement an enhanced diagnostic capability. The use of such techniques to explore RWD collected through the PUC1 protocol will serve to build a multi-modular clinical-research platform aimed at improving the predictive ability of the diagnosis of the development of comorbidities among different CoBraD. PUC2 thus aims to constitute a highly reliable and comprehensive platform of diagnostic modalities regarding complex brain disorders, and to

serve as a valuable support for experts in medical practice.

2.1.3 PUC3

MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication Reassessment

Objective *Identifying drugs with side effects on patients as well as with potential for repurposing.*

Status *PUC3 relies on the components and methods developed in PUC2 and goes in parallel with it, using the tools and analytical components to test real world therapies. Some specific aspects of it regarding the integration into the PUC2 components of RWD deriving from therapies and the connected repurposing and reassessment features have yet to be implemented*

PUC3 has the function of testing the protocol from a therapeutic point of view. In particular, it will be concerned with identifying the side effects of the drugs proposed to CoBraD patients, including psychosocial considerations. The aim of this PUC is therefore to advance scientific knowledge and understanding of the real-world therapies proposed for CoBraD patients and to tailor the most appropriate therapy for each type of patient, thereby personalising treatment and mitigating risks for the patient.

2.1.4 PUC4

MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Expert System

Objective *Assessing and managing complex brain disorders*

Status *PUC4 being an integration of all the previous PUCs will be developed and deployed in the latest stages of project development. In the actual phase of the project, there is developed a Platform Framework, where the knowledge resulted from Expert System can be displayed in a user friendly format. The API engine is ready to accommodate the functionality exposed by the Expert System. Authentication and Authorization mechanism is implemented, and available also for Expert System components.*

Finally, PUC4 aims at integrating the knowledge and know-how acquired through the implementation of all the previous PUCs to evaluate and test the Multidisciplinary Expert System, i.e. "a decision-making algorithm to achieve a medically relevant goal (diagnostic or therapeutic), mimicking or, ideally, surpassing a human expert". The objective of the final PUC is therefore to evaluate and test this system to try to make it prototypical for the assessment and management of CCCs.

In fact, to date, no platform unifies RWD and clinical and social analysis for CoBraD.

For a full and in-depth description of each PUC please refer to the D1.2 (Scientific, Technical and Innovation Roadmap) and to the D3.2, D3.3 (Project Manual–CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation – v1 and v2) and D4.3 deliverables.

At the time of this deliverable writing, the first two PUCS are in the execution and validation phase, while PUCs #3 and #4 are still in implementation phase.

The objective of the present assessment will therefore focused only on the PUCs #1 and #2, even though there are general elements common to all the PUCs, that will be evaluated as well. It should be noted that the objective of the present deliverable is not to evaluate the general idea and approach, something that has already been done during the grant assignment process, but to assess how what has been done in PUC1 and PUC2 comply with the MES-CoBraD Ethical and Legal Framework (see deliverable D2.3), as well as to ascertain the presence and adequacy of all the required documentation (IRB approvals, consent forms, information sheets). When evaluating the single PUC (here the #1 and the #2) we will also highlight which of the identified legal and ethical requirements do apply to it.

3 THE ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

The objective of this deliverable is to assess the conformity of the implementation of the PUCs with the ethical-legal framework outlined in D2.3 *The CoBraD ethical and regulatory framework* and with the requirements also highlighted in D2.1 *CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk*.

Hereafter, in 3.1 subsection, the ethical evaluation guidelines will be reported.

The applied assessment process will be illustrated in 3.2 subsection.

3.1 THE ETHICS EVALUATION GUIDELINES

Every scientific research has impacts on the people involved and on society as a whole, which is why it is crucial to have a clear mapping and reflection on the ethics criteria adopted during the conduct of research.

This need is even more stringent when considering the health and medical field, where research is conducted with the participation of (possibly vulnerable) people.

In fact, ethical reflection does not only consist of a theoretical aspect relating to critical reflection on abstract conceptual categories, but also deals with the elaboration of criteria, that are then used as a guideline for the correct execution of the research.

The IRB approval obtained by all the hospitals involved in the research (except KCL which is still pending) is in itself a valid confirmation of formal appropriateness and compliance with normative ethics and legal standards.

However, an in-depth reflection on how some of the research was conducted, and in particular a reflection on the consequences of artificial intelligence applied to a healthcare system, may provide us with a broader framework for interpreting the ethics/legal impacts of such research.

Furthermore, the MES-CoBraD project will require the participation of human participants. For this reason, the guidelines and the requirements that define the boundaries of what is ethically acceptable are of the utmost importance.

As we mentioned before, we elaborated an ethical framework for MES-CoBraD project in the D2.1 and in the D2.3 deliverables, where we stated how the Consortium will comply with the requirements identified in the DOA.

Following the seminal work of (T. L. Beauchamp & Childress, 2013) in the aforementioned deliverables we took as our guidance the four principles of bioethics as applied to healthcare, namely the principles of **respect for autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence and justice**.

Here, we identify for each of these broad principles the ethical requirements that the project must satisfy.

Even though these principles - dating back in their original formulation to 1779 - have been questioned (Huxtable, 2013; Shea, 2020; Takala, 2001) they still are at the basis of the contemporary speculations on bioethics and of medical practice (T. Beauchamp & Childress, 2019; T. L. Beauchamp & Childress, 2020; Lawrence, 2007) . We also took as a reference (The Belmont Report, 1979) that lead us to take a slightly different approach for what concerns the principle of autonomy, which in the report is, in fact, a sub principle of the broader “respect for persons”. If intended as for example in (Kraft et al., 2020) the principle of respect for persons may include aspects such as “empathy”, “caring”, “presence”, that are not included in the principle of autonomy. For this reason, in our evaluation, differently than in Beauchamp and Childress, we include “Autonomy” under “Respect for Persons” and we split in two this important principle, to be sure to take into account all its nuances.

For each of the four principles (“respect for persons”, “beneficence”, “non-maleficence”, “justice”) plus

the other two of “open science” and of “research safety and mutual duty of care” **we now introduce briefly the topic and state the requirements against which the MES-CoBraD PUCs will be assessed.**

3.1.1 PRINCIPLE OF RESPECT FOR PERSONS

As it was mentioned before, even though in the original work of Beauchamp and Childress the principle is that of “Autonomy” (that in the words of the two authors means “respecting and supporting autonomous decisions”), in this deliverable we embraced the widest approach deriving from the Belmont Report and we adopt as a guiding principle that of the “Respect for Persons” which includes the principle of Autonomy.

This means that on the one hand we considered all the implications of that principle: a decision is “autonomous” when it is made with complete freedom, without pressures, constraints or undue influence. But “freedom”, to be truly so, must also be based on adequate information and comprehension. Additionally, the influence of the context and of the boundary conditions must be considered. And, last but not least, MES-CoBraD is a project that is heavily based on the use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, something which adds an entire new dimension to the concept of autonomy, which, in our view, entails also the autonomy of the clinician and not only of the patient.

On the other hand, speaking of Respect of Persons instead than of Autonomy, means that we had to consider also requirements such as “to protect those with diminished autonomy”.or “to not be treated with judgmental attitude” or “to be set apart of the research outcomes” that do not pertain strictly to the autonomy and to the adequacy of information but that originate from a more holistic vision of the human being when implied in biomedical research.

To help distinguish these two semantic areas of the Respect for Persons principle we detailed the requirements for this principle in the two 3.1.1.1 (“Autonomy”) and 3.1.1.2 (“Respect”) subsections.

3.1.1.1 Autonomy

- Right to be adequately informed (about the benefits but also the risks of participating in the research, as well as about the duration of the participation and of everything such participation will entail), by the way of an information sheet and of a consent form
- The existence of validated procedures to collect the consent of a patient that is judged not to be able to take autonomous decisions
- Defined procedures to protect the participants with diminished autonomy or vulnerable
- Even stricter measures in case children are recruited
- The right to withdraw consent and to abandon the study at any moment, without suffering any consequence, and with clear and straightforward procedures
- The possibility to ask to a staff member any question, with a direct contact being given to the patient and possibly with multiple means of contacting him/her (telephone, email, etc.)
- The absence of any undue pressure or burden (for example the loss of the possibility of being cared for) or on the contrary of privileges (for example access to higher level care or payment) for the participation in the research (also see the Oviedo Convention - Additional Protocol concerning Biomedical Research, art. 12: “no undue influence, including that of a financial nature, will be exerted on persons to participate in research. In this respect, particular attention must be given to vulnerable or dependent persons”)
- The consideration for the context and for the individual characteristics of the patient (for example, if he/she has a low literacy, he/she must be given material and explanations he/she can understand, etc) and the respect for cultural sensitivities of participants and their communities
- The right to object to a diagnosis made by using the expert system
- For the clinician: the right to access the data on the basis of which certain decisions are taken

and the right to rectify such decisions

3.1.1.2 Respect

- The possibility to have a more profound and prolonged interaction with a trained clinician who will explain in detail all the details and the implications of participating in the research
- Allowing plenty of time to decide whether participate or not
- Listen to patients with attention and participation, showing interest for the participant as a person and not just as a source of useful data and appreciation for the participant's contribution to the research
- Researchers interact with prospect participants with empathy and non-judgmental attitude
- The availability of all the information in a language and formulation that the prospect participant can understand
- The right to be informed about the outcomes of the research and how the patient's participation contributed to the general results
- Should any previously unforeseen health condition emerge during the research, the patient has the right to be informed about it (Oviedo Convention - Additional protocol on...article 27 Duty of Care). An incidental findings policy exists and has been given to each participant.
- The right to know how the algorithm arrived at a certain decision or diagnosis (intersects with the principles of transparency and of explainability).

3.1.2 THE PRINCIPLE OF NON-MALEFICENCE

The principle of non-maleficence (as well as the principle of beneficence) has truly antique origins, dating back in one of its formulations to the hippocratic corpus and according to some studies (Smith, 2005) being formulated in its more known version (“primum non nocere”) by the English physician Thomas Sydenham in 1860. It is still the first guideline of any clinical practice, although - especially in biomedical research - it must be weighed against unavoidable considerations, namely that any medical action brings with it risks and potential side effects. In this respect this principle obviously intersects with the beneficence one, which states that any risk must be balanced by the potential advantages and benefits, either for the individual or (when doing research) for a similar class of individuals in the same condition or affected by the same disease. Given the nature of the MES-CoBraD research the main ethical risks are not related to the conduction of the research but to the use (and potential misuse) of the platform and of the expert system. In any case the project's consortium took great care to ensure that this principle is respected, considering in this also the aspects related to the presence of AI and of Machine Learning techniques. The principle of non-maleficence translates into the following requirements:

- The risks and burdens for the participants in the research must be limited in time and commensurate to the potential benefits
- The vulnerable persons participating in the research must be safeguarded. Specific and additional procedures must exist and be applied.
- It's clear how responsibility and legal liability would be allocated, there are procedures to request redress (Fanni et al., 2022), and they are known to participants
- The clinicians and all other healthcare professionals who will use the platform will be adequately trained. They must be able to use the platform and to understand its outputs
- The validity of the outputs of the platform will be adequately tested and verified, by scientifically validated means
- The system must be protected from cyber-attacks and data breaches. A recovery plan is in place in case of system failure or damage or breach
- Personal data of participants must be protected to avoid any possible inappropriate use and any damage deriving from it

- Measures should be taken to protect the patient/doctor relationship and avoid the risk of depersonalization of care and (from the clinician side) of depriving of sense the medical profession

3.1.3 THE PRINCIPLE OF BENEFICENCE

According to the Oviedo convention (Treaty No.164, 1997), and in particular to the Additional Protocol concerning Biomedical Research (Treaty No.195, 2005), “the interests and welfare of the human being participating in research shall prevail over the sole interest of society or science” (article 3) and “research shall not involve risks and burdens to the human being disproportionate to its potential benefits” (article 6). In fact, according to (T. L. Beauchamp & Childress, 2013), beneficence means from the one hand “relieving, lessening, or preventing harm” and from the other hand “providing benefits and balancing benefits against risks and costs “. In particular if biomedical research does not directly benefits the single participants, it can be conducted on humans only if “the research has the aim of contributing, through significant improvement in the scientific understanding of the individual's condition, disease or disorder, to the ultimate attainment of results capable of conferring benefit to the person concerned or to other persons in the same age category or afflicted with the same disease or disorder or having the same condition”(art 15.2, i) and if “the research entails only minimal risk and minimal burden for the individual concerned” (art 15.2, ii). These general principles in MES-CoBraD translate into the following requirements:

- The research must be beneficial to the single participant, and the way in which this happens must be explicitly stated and explained;
- If this is not the case, it must be ascertained that the research contributes to achieving significant results for persons being in the same condition or affected by the same disease;
- The risks and burdens for the single participant must be proportionate to the potential benefits.

3.1.4 THE PRINCIPLE OF JUSTICE

Beauchamp and Childress define justice as “a cluster of norms for fairly distributing benefits, risks, and costs” in thus adopting a vision of justice mainly distributive: no one group, may it be based on gender, racial, ethnic, or socioeconomic criteria, should be disproportionately burdened or benefited by the research. It should be noted that this concept of distributive justice applies to classes, not to individuals. Thus, an issue may arise if we want to adopt the point of view of the single participant. Another issue is represented by the correct representation of each group or class into the research, which is a precondition of fair distribution and of equity and that reflects on the group composition of a clinical trial. The selection of subjects, as it is powerfully underlined in the Belmont report, it’s a crucial aspect of ensuring justice in biomedical research, because not choosing the most appropriate subjects may end in results that are not accurate but also because the burdens of research (as when the research takes place in underdeveloped countries) may be placed on a group of people who will not enjoy its benefits. But more than this, it is a warning against any discrimination and against any decision making made on the basis of stereotypes or of other unfair misconceptions or assumptions. For instance, a continuous mis representation of certain groups may end in also denying the benefits of research to this group (as it happens in many drugs that are studied more on men than women and so are less effective on women). The aim of MES-CoBraD project is to develop a system that - if adopted and when fully operative - might have a strong influence on health policies of the participating countries. For this reason, the Consortium agreed in the DOA to make any effort to avoid any form of discrimination, either in the course of the research and as the result of its outputs. A particular attention will be paid to sex and gender issues, both internal to the Consortium and in participants recruitment and management. The principle of justice translates into MES-CoBraD in the following requirements:

- Ensure that a correct and fairly representative group composition is achieved by all clinical

partners, with inclusion and exclusion criteria defined based on sound scientific principles and respecting the following KPIs:

- Participant female to male ratio ≈ 1.0 (range 0.8 – 1.2)
 - % of participants belonging to an ethnic, socioeconomic, or gender minority $\geq 10\%$
 - Congruence of participant socioeconomic background to respective community ≥ 0.7
 - % of clinicians evaluating participants who completed feedback questionnaires on MES-CoBraD Platform and Protocol $\geq 95\%$
 - % of participants completing questionnaires on satisfaction in using the MES-CoBraD compared to standard healthcare practices $\geq 80\%$
- Define procedures and mitigation actions to avoid the misuse of the MES-CoBraD platform (for example to profile people for insurance purposes)
 - Strongly avoid the presence of algorithmic biases and the generation of misdiagnosis or under diagnosis at scale and apply appropriate debiasing techniques
 - Strictly avoid any discrimination in group composition both between patients and between researchers based on sex, gender, race, religion, ethnicity, while a correct sex and gender balance as well as of ethnicity is achieved
 - Do not discriminate health personnel or researchers as a consequence of their inability to use MES-CoBraD
 - Make available the positive results of MES-CoBraD to a vast audience of beneficiaries (overlapping with the principles of fairness of research and of open science).

There are more general principles (not pertaining specifically to biomedical research) that also the consortium agreed to respect and that will be outlined in the following sections.

3.1.5 THE PRINCIPLE OF OPEN SCIENCE

The respect of the Open Science principle will be ensured by the following requirements:

- The results – also the intermediate ones – of the research are transparent, duly disseminated and freely available
- The public fundings received and how they have been used is transparent
- Data are FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
- Citizens are encouraged and put in a position to actively participate and contribute to the research (citizen science)
- All staff (not only medical or scientific) participating in the research is properly educated and trained and that eventual gaps are closed by the participation in training or other education programs
- A working environment is created respectful and supportive, designed to aim at excellence in research and reflective of the open science principles.

3.1.6 THE PRINCIPLE OF RESEARCH SAFETY AND OF MUTUAL DUTY OF CARE

The respect of the principle of Research safety and Mutual duty of care will be ensured by the following requirements:

- The safety and well-being (also psychological) of all the personnel engaged in the research is preserved
- The impacts on the society as a whole have been assessed and are positive, also considering indirect impacts such as how the complex brain diseases are perceived and paid attention to
- Potential misuses of the research and of the platform have been assessed and that appropriate mitigation measures are enforced
- The opinions and feedbacks of those participating in the research are gathered and used (according with the participatory health research paradigm (Groot et al., 2018))

- Vulnerable individuals are recognized as such, not discriminated or put in a situation of discomfort and are actively protected
- The care needs of patients as well as of researchers and of all other individuals implied in the research are actively monitored and taken into account and a collaborative and positive communicative environment is created, where mutual help and communication are the guiding principles of any action (following the ethics of care “pillars”: caring with, caring about, caring for, care giving, care receiving) (J C Tronto, 1998; Maio, 2017).

The above illustrated principles and requirements do apply to all the PUCs, even if in the present deliverable only the #1 and the #2 PUCs will be evaluated, due to the timing of development of the other two PUCs. More details about PUCs are in 2.1 section.

3.2 THE ASSESSMENT PROCESS

The assessment process applied during the previous months of project was carried out through the following steps:

1. Desktop assessment of the information found in all existing project documentation regarding the description and development of the PUCs (currently only the first two) to create a knowledge baseline.
2. Comparison of the results of the desktop assessment with the ethics evaluation guidelines reported in 3.1 section.
3. Gathering and analysis of further information on the status and mode of execution of each PUC through a self-assessment questionnaire circulated among the consortium partners (medical and technical).
4. Comparison of the desktop assessment results with the outcomes of the self-assessment, to see if mismatches or noticeable differences emerge between what has been declared and the actual implementation.
5. Revision and reporting of the data protection assessment already done in the previous project months.

3.2.1 DESKTOP ASSESSMENT

First of all, the desktop assessment consisted in a review of all the current released deliverables and documentation realised by the consortium partners where the PUCs are described. In coordination with the consortium, the list of relevant deliverables and documentation is the following:

The DOA (general description of the PUCs)

- D1. 2 - Scientific, Technical and Innovation Map (general description of the PUCs)
- D3.1 and D3.2 - Project Manual v1 and v2 (general description of the PUCs)
- D5.1 - Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security (PUC2 - Data gathering)
- D5.2- Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security - final (PUC2 - Data gathering)
- D6.1 - Advanced analytics prototype (PUC2 - Data analysis)
- D7.1 - System requirement and architecture (PUC2 - system architecture)
- D8.2 - MES- CoBraD validation framework (PUC1 - Real World Data acquisition)
- D8.3. D8.4 - Participant recruitment, pre-existing RWD access, Prospective RWD acquisition and secure storage (PUC1 - Real World Data acquisition)

Furthermore, we analysed the minutes of scientific meetings and of External Advisory Board meetings and we accessed working documents on the RWD questionnaires and the group selection. Of course, we examined IRB applications and approvals, consent forms and information sheets of each medical partner.

3.2.2 ANALYSIS OF THE SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

We submitted an ethics questionnaire to partners, with the aim of acquiring information about the actual practices that we couldn't locate into the deliverables and in the other documentation we examined. Partners were also invited to express their point of view even on complex or speculative ethical questions, in accordance with the requirements of the open science and mutual duty of care (improving communication between partners and enhance the expression of ideas and points of views). The questionnaire responses were then analysed against the evaluation ethics guidelines stated in 3.1 subsection.

The outcomes of the questionnaire are presented in section 6 while the questions are in Annex I

3.2.3 EVALUATION OF THE DESKTOP ASSESSMENT AGAINST THE ETHICS EVALUATION GUIDELINES

In this step we examined for each PUC whether what has been described in the deliverables and thus done so far by the consortium truly addresses the general ethical and legal issues highlighted in 3.1 section.

Results of this analysis is described in sections 4 and 5.

3.2.4 COMPARISON OF THE SELF ASSESSMENT AGAINST THE DESKTOP ASSESSMENT

After collecting the relevant data through the two above-described assessments, the results of the desktop assessment were compared against the results of the self-assessment to understand the eventual coincidence or discrepancy between the actual practices as perceived by the researchers and what is described and declared in the delivered reports. The aim was to identify possible areas of improvement with respect to how the Consortium is incorporating the ethical and legal requirements into the research. It also helped us to identify process mistakes or issues or communication errors.

Results of this analysis is described in section 7.

3.2.5 DATA PROTECTION ASSESSMENT

An assessment of the normative elements of MES-CoBraD is developed in the Ethical and Regulatory Framework (D2.3) and the Data Management Plan (D2.2). The main findings are summarised in section 8.

4 DESKTOP EVALUATION OF PUC1 AGAINST THE ETHICS GUIDELINES

As we already described in the general introduction, the first pilot use case (PUC1) lies at the hearth of the entire project, representing a concrete example of how the MES-CoBraD consortium wants to approach the complexity of the diagnosis and care of the complex brain diseases (from now on: CoBraD).

PUC1 is where real world data from patients both prospective and retrospective, is gathered according to the project's protocol and then used to nurture a database (a "data lake") that will be used by the WP6 and the WP5 to perform the automated analyses.

But the novelty of the PUC1 approach is not the fact that data are gathered and then put into a database; the important point is that four medical partners across various nations (EU and not EU) all agreed on a common protocol which implies to assess not only one disease but several (epilepsy, dementia and sleep disorders) through a predefined period of time using agreed on questionnaires and clinical examinations and trying with this to understand not only the etiology and the course of a certain disease, but also the comorbidity between different syndromes and their reciprocal influence, as well as to spot whether there are common factors that do have an impact on the diseases.

This is an extremely interesting approach, both from the individual and from the societal point of view, as it might have impacts on the individual care but also on the policies and decisions that are taken at a higher and more general level (for example it could have an influence on healthcare policies of a country or – as an effect of the inclusion in the protocol of people from diverse socio-economic and ethnics conditions in different countries – it might minimize existing albeit unintentional discrimination against minorities).

In the deliverables D2.1 and D2.3, we outlined an ethical and legal framework, furtherly detailed and itemized in section 3.1 of the present deliverable, stating the parameters to which any such research should conform and also declaring how the MES-CoBraD consortium did intend to respect such parameters.

Moving from the analysis on the materials produced and released so far by the consortium, this section will examine whether the documents content truly addresses the ethical and legal issues highlighted in the two aforementioned deliverables and if it respects the declared parameters.

For each parameter, the problem, how it should be addressed in general, the state of advancement of the PUC1 in this respect and its compliance (ethically and/or legally) will be briefly described.

4.1 RESPECT FOR PERSONS

4.1.1 AUTONOMY

Table 1: Desktop assessment for the PUC1 of the Autonomy Requirements

Requirement	Implementation
<i>Right to be adequately informed (about the benefits but also the risks of participating in the research, as well as about the duration of the participation and of everything such participation will entail), by the way of an information sheet and of a consent form</i>	<i>Information sheets and consent forms are given to prospect patients. They are available in Annex III of the D2.6. They explain thoroughly all the details of the eventual participation in the research, including the risks and the burdens. Furthermore, in the submission for IRB approvals the recruitment and consent procedures are described, as well as the protocols for clinical evaluation.</i>
<i>The existence of validated</i>	<i>From the available documentation (see Annexes IV and section</i>

Requirement	Implementation
<p>procedures to collect the consent of a patient that is judged not to be able to take autonomous decisions</p> <p>Defined procedures to protect the participants with diminished autonomy or vulnerable</p>	<p>3.2 and 3.2.2 of the D2.6) it emerges that if a patient is not able to take autonomous decisions the consent will be asked to his/her legal tutor.</p> <p>From the work of (McDonald et al., 2016) we extracted some possible additional safeguards some of which are already applied in MES-CoBraD:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The presence of someone (family member, caregiver, etc) they are familiar with and who they trust (applied, see Annexes IV and section 3.2.2 of the D2.6, and section 6 below) • Give enough time to think about their participation (applied, see Annex II and III of the D2.6) • Being recruited by researchers trained to work with people with disabilities, with diminished autonomy or mentally impaired and having a long experience in this (applied, see Annex II of the D2.6) • Being recruited by someone with disabilities • Letting the legal tutor decide for them (applied, see Annex IV of the D2.6) • Using respectful language (to be ascertained via the User Acceptance Tests) • Personalized approach: not every individual with disabilities or vulnerable is the same (to be ascertained, focus group with partners)
<p>Even stricter measures in case children are recruited</p>	<p>Children will not be recruited. The only partner who will recruit them (see NIA selection criteria) received IRB approval and complies with EU regulations.</p>
<p>The right to withdraw consent and to abandon the study at any moment, without suffering any consequence, and with clear and straightforward procedures</p>	<p>Patients can abandon at any moment (from the documentation it emerges that in fact some patients already did). The procedure to stop participating in the study although different for any partner is in any case really simple and varies from contacting a member of the research staff to sending an email. It is detailed in the information sheet and consent form (see Annex III of the D2.6)</p>
<p>The possibility to ask to a staff member any question, with a direct contact being given to the patient and possibly with multiple means of contacting him/her (telephone, email, etc)</p>	<p>The participants in the research are given the contact information of a staff member to whom they can address for any doubt</p>
<p>The absence of any undue pressure or burden (for example the loss of the possibility of being cared for) or on the contrary of privileges (for example access to higher level care or payment) for the participation in the research (also see the Oviedo Convention - Additional Protocol concerning Biomedical Research (Treaty</p>	<p>This is clearly specified in the information sheets. See Annex III of the D2.6</p>

Requirement	Implementation
No.195, 2005), art. 12: no undue influence, including that of a financial nature, will be exerted on persons to participate in research. In this respect, particular attention must be given to vulnerable or dependent persons”)	
The consideration for the context and for the individual characteristics of the patient (for example, if he/she has a low literacy, he/she must be given material and explanations he/she can understand) and the respect for cultural sensitivities of participants and their communities	The written material which is given to the participants (see Annex III of the D2.6) is written in a fairly simple manner, with every detail clearly specified. However, this is no insurance that people effectively understand it. In any case written material is accompanied and supplemented by interviews (see section 3.2 of the D2.6 and section 6), either by phone or in person (or both) and the patient has the possibility of addressing any question.

4.1.2 RESPECT

Table 2: Desktop assessment for the PUC1 of the Respect requirements

Requirement	Implementation
The possibility to have a more profound and prolonged interaction with a trained clinician who will explain in detail all the details and the implications of participating in the research	See Annex III and section 3.2 of the D2.6. In any case, this varies accordingly to the participants management procedures of the different clinical partners, but in general participants do have a direct contact of a researcher/clinician who is available to clarify all questions.
Allowing enough time to decide whether participate or not	In the information sheets, patients are explicitly invited to “take their time” to think about their participation (see Annex III of the D2.6)
Listen to patients with attention and participation, showing interest for the participant as a person and not just as a source of useful data and appreciation for the participant’s contribution to the research	This will be verified through the User Acceptance Tests (from now on: “UAT”), if dedicated questions will be included as per our suggestion. Also see section 6 below (results of the self-assessment).
Gather and make use of participant’s feedback and opinions	In the D8.2 the UAT are described. Participants in the research, including the patients, are given the opportunity of assessing the platform and the pilots from their point of view. However, the patients are never asked about how they are treated, their interaction with researchers, and also if they feel they have received enough information prior their engagement and during and afterwards their participation. This may be the effect of a disregard of the subjective feelings and sensations of the participants that if one wants to take into account seriously the principle of the respect for persons should instead be greatly prized.

Requirement	Implementation
	Also, apart from registering the participants' answers on a Likert scale there should also be given to the participants the possibility of giving open answers so that they can express their feedbacks more extensively and freely.
Researchers interact with prospect participants with empathy and non-judgmental attitude	This will be ascertainable through the UATs and/or by means of dedicated focus groups
The availability of all the information in a language and formulation that the prospect participant can understand	The information sheets and consent forms are provided in the mother tongue of patients (Greek, English, Hebrew or Spanish). Everything else is in English. In the D3.3 deliverable the fact that some of the questions are poorly understood by patients is undertaken. It is said that the protocol will be modified to solve this issue and that questions were reviewed by the staff with patients ("Questions are reviewed by staff with patients and caregivers and plans for either clarifying to patients or for modifying the questions are in place as the pilot protocol is developed" (D3.3 table 9)
The right to be informed about the outcomes of the research and how the patient's participation contributed to the general results	In the available documentation this aspect is not specified. However, from the questionnaire emerged that people will be informed through a website or through other means (emails, telephone calls, etc. Please refer to the section 6 for full details). For the partners who rely solely on the website, to completely fulfil this requirement it would be necessary a way of informing the participants that are conducted on a more one-to-one basis and in any case of push nature (participants are actively sent information and do not have to search for it)
Should any previously unforeseen health condition emerge during the research, the patient has the right to be informed about it (Oviedo Convention - Additional protocol on...article 27 Duty of Care). An incidental findings policy exists and has been given to each participant.	The incidental findings policies can be found in Annex II of the D2.6. The participants will be informed about anything connected to their health that emerges during their participation in the research. See also section 6.

4.2 NON MALEFICENCE

Table 3: Desktop assessment for the PUC1 of the Non Maleficence Requirements

Requirement	Implementation
The risks and burdens for the participants in the research must be limited in time and commensurate to the potential benefits	The duration of the research is clearly specified in the information sheet (see Annex III of the D2.6) as well as the potential burdens and benefits. Being research that evaluates diseases that for the diagnosis don't require invasive analysis the potential burdens are quite limited (see documents in Annex III and section 3.2.5 of the D2.6 for a complete list). As it is evident by the information sheets (see Annex III of the D2.6) and in the D3.1, D3.2 and D1.2, the potential benefits at the individual level lie mostly in the discovery of potential

Requirement	Implementation
	<i>undiagnosed comorbidities or of other diseases often discovered in the course of these kind of analyses as well as in the possibility of accessing to a deep phenotype, which is not always available if not included in a study such this one . Of course, at the societal level the potential advantages are huge, something which, also on the basis of Oviedo Convention - Additional Protocol concerning Biomedical Research, is sufficient to counterbalance the individual burdens.</i>
<i>The vulnerable persons participating in the research must be safeguarded. Specific and additional procedures must exist and be applied.</i>	<i>The procedures for the management of vulnerable individuals can be found in section 3.2.2 of the D2.6. Please refer also to the analogous point in the “respect for persons” section.</i>
<i>It's clear how responsibility and legal liability would be allocated, there are procedures to request redress, especially when AI is involved, and they are known to participants</i>	<i>This is not evident from the available documentation. In case also from the questionnaire do not emerge the presence of a sufficient awareness on this point measure should be taken to raise the attention of the consortium. From the answers to the self-assessment questionnaire (see section 6below) it emerges that the ES is considered only as an aid not a decision maker and for this reason the responsibility chain is not considered modified by the introduction of the ES (Naik et al., 2022).</i>

4.3 BENEFICENCE

Table 4: Desktop assessment for the PUC1 of the Beneficence Requirements

Requirement	Implementation
<i>The research must be beneficial to the single participant, and the way in which this happens must be explicitly stated and explained</i>	<i>As per the Oviedo Convention, the benefits for the participation in biomedical research can also not apply directly to the single participant but to the same class of participants (people being in the same condition or suffering from the same disease). In this respect benefits are even more clear, since the aim of the MES-CoBraD research is precisely to improve diagnosis and care for an entire class of brain diseases. The benefits for the participants are explained in the information sheets (see Annex III)</i>
<i>If this is not the case, it must be ascertained that the research contributes to achieving significant results for persons being in the same condition or affected by the same disease</i>	<i>This is the object and the main aim of the entire MES-CoBraD project</i>
<i>The risks and burdens for the single participant must be proportionate to the potential benefits</i>	<i>Fortunately, especially in PUC1 (as specified in the D3.2. D8.3 and in the information sheets), the risks and burdens of participating in the research are quite mild. That being the case, it appears evident that this requirement is satisfied.</i>

4.4 JUSTICE

Table 5: Desktop assessment for the PUC1 of the Justice Requirements

Requirement	Implementation
<p>Ensure that a correct and fairly representative group composition is achieved by all clinical partners, with inclusion and exclusion criteria defined based on sound scientific principles and respecting the following KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participant female to male ratio ≈ 1.0 (range 0.8 – 1.2) • % of participants belonging to an ethnic, socioeconomic, or gender minority $\geq 10\%$ • Congruence of participant socioeconomic background to respective community ≥ 0.7 • % of clinicians evaluating participants who completed feedback questionnaires on MES-CoBraD Platform and Protocol $\geq 95\%$ • % of participants completing questionnaires on satisfaction in using the MES-CoBraD compared to standard healthcare practices $\geq 80\%$ 	<p>The recruitment of the prospective participants it's one of the most important and critical steps of any clinical research and must be done with great care, because not only it has a great influence on the research outcomes but also has notable ethical implications.</p> <p>The criteria MES-CoBraD is going to adopt to recruit participants are detailed in the D2.1 deliverable, section 4.1. In particular the Consortium is bound to respect the following requisites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • freedom to decide whether to participate or not • non-discrimination in case of refusal • protection of privacy and of personal data • sufficient amount of time to decide • absence of pressures of any kind: participants must be free from coercion and influence • protection of fragile people with dedicated procedures • inclusion/exclusion criteria determined on the basis of scientific principles • a group composition that mirrors what is statistically the composition of the context in which the research takes place is sought, thus minimizing the potential for bias • ensure that full and complete information is given to potential participants • eventual side or negative effects are clearly described and understood • a contact for further information is given to prospective participants <p>In the D3.2 (Project Manual v2) Annex II there is a synthetic recap of real world data categories and sub-categories being acquired, among which do appear social information categories (i.e. employment, income, housing, education years, highest diploma, religious affinity, developmental history, childhood trauma) which is a clear indicator that also important not-biological factors are being taken into account</p> <p>Before enrolling any participants, a detailed interview is being conducted by an expert researcher, who is able to fully explain the details of the research and who is also skilled enough to evaluate if the prospect participant is able to understand what he/she is engaging into and if he/she can sensibly answer the questions.</p> <p>The actual recruitment procedures and outcomes have been described in the D8.3, D8.4 deliverables, where both prospective and retrospective data gathering strategies and results are outlined.</p> <p>The KPIs for the group composition are listed in the Grant Agreement and then confirmed in the deliverable D1.2 Table 1.</p>

Requirement	Implementation
	<p><i>From the D8.3 it's not clear whether all the KPIs have been met or what is the status of achievement. However more information emerged from the questionnaire, whose results are reported in section 6. Here we can anticipate that not all the KPIs have been met still, but that the partners are actively working to meet the objectives relative to this point.</i></p> <p><i>While it is evident that some KPIs have not been reached still, it is also clear that RWD is being taken in agreement with the recruitment and group composition procedures detailed above, and that many data are already being collected.</i></p> <p><i>Another aspect to take into consideration - as stated by (Emanuel et al., 2000) is that the selection of participants should be done only following scientific criteria, namely trying to maximize the positive effect of the inclusion (or exclusion) of a certain participant or group of participants for the scientific aims of the research, and never for reasons of commodity or simplicity (for example selection of people who for any reason are easier to enrol).</i></p> <p><i>In MES-CoBraD it appears evident that every effort is being made to enrol people who are significant for the research (having a brain disease and/or being part of a minority or of other identified classes). Even when no particular selection is made it's because people enrolling are patients who suffer from one or more complex brain disease and so are per se interesting.</i></p> <p><i>No prisoners or people in condition of being subjects of undue pressures are selected.</i></p>
<p><i>Any discrimination in group composition both between patients and between researchers based on sex, gender, race, religion, ethnicity, is strictly avoided and That on the contrary a correct sex and gender balance as well as of ethnicity is achieved</i></p>	<p><i>Some of the KPIs, as outlined in 1.2 deliverable, are precisely about this (gender, religion, ethnicity): there should be certain percentages of people who are female, who are part of a minority, etc.</i></p> <p><i>As it is stated in the D3.2 (project manual v2) section 2.5 sex and gender considerations are considered of the utmost importance in the project and will be faced with an intersectionality approach, in thus considering also other factors, such as education, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, etc.</i></p> <p><i>As per sex and gender issues, there is a dedicated deliverable ("Sex and gender requirements" D3.4) and they will be the object of a dedicated deliverable (D3.8 due in month 36) but the partners are already working on them, distributing a questionnaire on sex and gender issues inside the consortium. For the outcomes of the sex and gender internal questionnaire please see the 3.3 section of the D2.6</i></p>
<p><i>The positive results of MES-CoBraD are available to a vast audience of beneficiaries (in this overlapping with the principles of fairness of research and of open science)</i></p>	<p><i>The consortium agreed to the open science principles, that imply also a positive effort towards dissemination and condision of results. Also datasets will be made available (after having been duly anonymized or depersonalized) to other researchers. The positive results of MES-CoBraD are</i></p>

Requirement	Implementation
	<i>conceived to be of help to a vast audience, both of clinicians (that will be helped in their daily practice) and of patients, that in the end will be able to access to a better diagnosis and care process.</i>

4.5 OPEN SCIENCE

Table 6: Desktop assessment for the PUC1 of the Open Science Requirements

Requirement	Implementation
<i>The results - also the intermediate ones - of the research are transparent, duly disseminated and freely available</i>	<p><i>The deliverables that are not public will be kept reserved. However, they can be accessed by members of the the EC. Public deliverables instead can be accessed and read from anyone.</i></p> <p><i>There is a dedicated WP (WP9) for dissemination whose activities to date found concretization in the following deliverables:</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;"><i>Communication & Dissemination Plan, Business and Exploitation Plan, Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities Report and Plan</i></p>
<i>The public fundings received and how they have been used is transparent</i>	<i>The consortium, as in every EU project, is bind to justify and report every expense</i>
<i>The data are FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)</i>	<i>The consortium agree that even after the end of the projects the data will be accessible and reusable for other research agents (cfr. Grant Agreement 1.2: "Once securely stored on the Platform, the information will be accessible to Consortium and external clinicians, researchers and organizations towards promoting health of CCC worldwide" and D2.2 ("Data Management Plan") section 2.1, dedicated to fair data principles)</i>
<i>Citizens are encouraged and put in a position to actively participate (Denecke et al., 2021) and contribute to the research (citizen science)</i>	<i>To foster societal participation with MES-CoBraD, citizen scientists were identified as a stakeholder group that the project would try to engage and involve in activities. The stakeholder engagement strategy (D3.6) defines this group and discusses how they should be reached</i>
<i>All staff (not only medical or scientific) participating in the research is properly educated and trained and that eventual gaps are closed by the participation in training or other education programs</i>	<i>MES-CoBraD Consortium members are among the most advanced research centers on CoBraD, with several peer reviewed studies and publications and engaged in daily clinical practice. Their competencies have been evaluated during the assignment of the grant.</i>
<i>A working environment is created respectful and supportive, designed to aim at excellence in research and reflective of the open</i>	<i>In MES-CoBraD the cooperation and interaction between researchers and group members is truly enhanced through the frequent recurring meetings (biweekly plenary and scientific meetings, Work Group 4 on interdisciplinary hypothesis testing,</i>

Requirement	Implementation
science principles	<p>single work groups meetings).</p> <p>The opinions and findings of every consortium member is listened to and attentively discussed.</p> <p>Furthermore, meetings with the external advisory board are organized where an external opinion is given and discussed on the latest findings of the consortium.</p> <p>There is a dedicated work group on the “science of science” to help the consortium to adopt the best practices in scientific research.</p> <p>The following KPI although not solely on this is interesting as it evaluates the impact of MES-CoBraD on labour through an internal assessment: % clinicians and scientists who completed feedback questionnaires on labour and health policy impact of advanced analytics use in clinical and research practice</p>

4.6 RESEARCH SAFETY AND MUTUAL DUTY OF CARE

Table 7: Desktop assessment for the PUC1 of the Research Safety and mutual duty of care requirements

Requirement	Implementation
The safety and well being (also psychological) of all the personnel engaged in the research is preserved	The MES-CoBraD research does not imply working in dangerous environments or having contact with dangerous substances or machinery. All the partners, as per their internal policies, are engaged in providing to all their staff a sane and safe working environment. Cfr also the D2.6 section 3.3 for the results of the internal sex and gender questionnaire where some aspects of the working environment are examined.
The impacts on the society as a whole have been assessed and are positive, also considering indirect impacts such as how the complex brain diseases are perceived and paid attention to	As stated in the Project Manual (D3.1 and D3.3) the impacts on the society if the research is crowned with success would be extremely positive, achieving a better diagnosis and care of complex brain diseases that are affecting a large part of the population having huge impacts on people’s lives. But, even if the research would not completely meet its objectives, the approach is to be considered particularly interesting and capable of raising attention on a problem (that of the co-morbidities and in general of the brain diseases) that would surely be positive if it ends in more research oriented in that direction. Not to be forgotten the fact that the data that will be collected for the project will be reusable also by other projects and researchers, something really precious if we consider the difficulty of doing research and collecting data with human participants.
The potential misuses of the research and of the platform have been assessed and that appropriate mitigation measures are enforced	Not evident from the available documentation. There are cybersecurity measures (please refer to D2.2 Annex VII) but other measures to prevent potential misuses could be implemented, for example the full anonymization of data (please refer to the section 8 for the legal assessment and to the D2.3 and D2.2 (data management plan) for a description

Requirement	Implementation
	<p><i>of de-personalization measures undertaken by the Consortium). As in every healthcare expert system there is the risk of it being used for social scoring, but the question remains open whether there could be a way of avoiding it already in the design phase.</i></p>
<p><i>The opinions and feedbacks of those participating in the research is gathered and used (according with the participatory health research paradigm (Siffels et al., 2021))</i></p>	<p><i>UAT will be done and users feedback will be collected. This is evident particularly from the deliverable 8.2 where the user acceptance tests are described.</i></p> <p><i>We noticed that questions about how patients felt and the relationship between doctor/researcher and patients are missing, while from the point of view of the ethics of care but also of the respect for persons requirement would in our opinion be necessary.</i></p>
<p><i>Vulnerable individuals are recognized as such, not discriminated or put in a situation of discomfort and are actively protected</i></p>	<p><i>As stated above vulnerable persons will be adequately protected</i></p>
<p><i>The care needs of patients as well as of researchers and of all other persons implied in the research are actively monitored and taken into account and that a collaborative and positive communicative environment is created, where mutual help and communication are the cornerstones of work and care relationships (following the ethics of care “pillars”: caring with, caring about, caring for, care giving, care receiving)</i></p>	<p><i>It is not possible to deduce the respect of this requirement from the existing documentation. It will be necessary to hold a focus group with clinicians and/or patients to understand if and how this requirement is being respected.</i></p>

5 DESKTOP EVALUATION OF PUC2 AGAINST THE ETHICS GUIDELINES

AI systems can be a useful and important resource for many different health-related activities. For instance, deep learning has shown substantial improvements in e.g., data augmentation and image classification (for instance gene expressions, MRI scans, etc (Chaudhari et al., 2019)).

Of even greater interest are the new approaches based on Generative Adversarial Networks (Tanaka & Aranha, 2019), to increase the pool of medical data on which to train Machine Learning systems capable of recognising certain types of cancer through imaging. These techniques, called Data Augmentation (Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019), pose even greater challenges from a regulatory perspective, as the data used to train AI systems are themselves synthetically generated by AI systems.

Furthermore, AI can act as a tool to support and amplify human cognitive functions for clinicians providing care to patients with complex diseases (Bini, 2018).

Such developments require an in-depth analysis on how the use of such technologies is changing the concepts of illness, care, medical practice and the care relationship within our societies.

In addition, it is relevant to understand how clinical decision-making processes are being challenged by the rise of so-called artificial intelligence-based decision support systems (AI-DSS) and how these change not only the ways of interaction within medical practice, but also how they impact the conditions of accountability, transparency and responsibility.

One of the biggest opportunities that collaborative AI systems applied in healthcare contexts impose is the modification of healthcare practice and work.

How will collaborative AI systems enhance the diagnostic and treatment capabilities of healthcare workers? How will the integration of technological elements for prediction and diagnosis into traditional medical practice change the concept of care, body, disease?

Furthermore, how should responsibility be attributed in the event of an error, overdiagnosis or underdiagnosis, wrong treatment or damage?

These issues are currently being debated in the scientific community. They have already been introduced in the D2.3 and in the current document and will continue to be addressed by the MES-CoBraD consortium, in the Work Groups specifically dedicated to analysing these issues and in future activities (such as the ETHAI Model).

The deliverables that will be subject of the analysis in this section will be the 5.1 (data integration, harmonization, sharing and security), the 6.1 (advanced analytics prototype) and the 7.1 (systems requirement and architecture). It should be noticed that the objective of the PUC2 is the analysis, through AI and Machine Learning techniques, of the RWD acquired through the PUC1. This is the reason why all these three deliverables are relevant. Also, the Data Management Plan (D2.2) will be taken into account.

It should however be pointed out that the PUC2 does not include the entire AI and ML component of the project, something that will only be possible through the PUC4, scheduled for the end of the project.

As a consequence, some of the ethics requirements cannot be fully assessed and satisfied at this moment due to the fact that the artificial intelligence modules are still not fully operational. Just to make an example, all the questions concerning the accountability at the moment can only be answered theoretically, since the system is still not delivering outputs; in the same way, the questions concerning biases can only be approached from the group composition and datasets point of view, since the ML algorithms have not been applied to those data. A more complete evaluation of the aspects concerning the application of the Artificial Intelligence and of the Machine Learning to healthcare in MES-CoBraD will be done in D3.9 (ETHAI MODEL) and in D2.8 (the v2 of the present deliverable).

5.1 RESPECT FOR PERSONS

5.1.1 AUTONOMY

Table 8: Desktop assessment for the PUC2 of the Autonomy requirements

Requirement	Implementation
<p>The right to object to a diagnosis made by using the expert system</p>	<p>At the moment of the present deliverable the expert system is still not developed. But, since any diagnoses will pass through human agents, the patient's right to object is the same as when no expert system is involved.</p> <p>See section 6 for the outputs of the ethical questionnaire on this</p>
<p>For the clinician: the right to access the data on the basis of which certain decisions are taken and the right to rectify any such decisions</p>	<p>In the D5.1 there are the following requirements that apply and speak for the respect of this requirement:</p> <p>ES-1 Expert System The system shall provide an Expert System to guide clinical decisions by providing feedback from both patients and clinicians.</p> <p>ES-4 User control over next step(s) of DSS/ES The system shall allow the user to choose the next step (from the list or outside it), depending on options provided in Visualization per Step of DSS/ES output.</p> <p>ES-5 Coordination aide module - scheduling The system shall allow the coordinator/user to be informed of upcoming steps (e.g., scheduling a specific participant, or calling someone), based on the pilot protocol process of a study.</p> <p>ES-9 Visualize flow of actions The system shall allow to visualize flow of actions that reflect the protocol.</p> <p>ES-13 ES - Guided steps The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables. Each task will be categorized and will allow to use metadata information for better future recommendations.</p> <p>ES-14 Automated report/message generator The system shall generate a report either for feedback to the patient or for use by a clinician, based on the data entered in a specific function.</p> <p>DAN-11 Generation of a report as output The Data Analytics Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the</p>

Requirement	Implementation
	<p><i>QRB Component. Next, at each stage of applying algorithms for analysing and processing the data, the Data Analytics Component should be able to save which programming language, i.e., Python, MATLAB, R, etc. and library, i.e., SciPy, Nilearn, MNE, etc. was used for conducting the respective experiments. Finally, after the user has completed all the analyses, the system shall be able to export a file, which will include the programming language and the libraries used for each specific analysis.</i></p> <p>AI-4</p> <p><i>AI based natural language processing reports</i></p> <p><i>The system shall produce customizable / configurable reports, dashboards and visualizations based on NLP analysis</i></p>

5.1.2 RESPECT

Table 9: Desktop assessment Desktop assessment for the PUC2 of the respect for persons requirements

Requirement	Implementation
<p><i>The right to know how the algorithm arrived at a certain decision or diagnosis (intersects with the principles of transparency and of explainability)</i></p>	<p><i>Since the MES-CoBraD outputs and diagnoses will be always mediated by a human, from the point of view of the patient this requirement does not change what happens in the normal clinical practice. From the point of view of the clinician instead, the system will have a way to report the way in which it arrived at its outputs.</i></p> <p><i>This aspect is dealt for in the deliverable 6.1: in the section 2.1 the evidence-based medicine - that the consortium intends to adopt - is thoroughly explained as well as the relevance given within its framework to the patients' point of view and feedbacks; in the section 2.5.4 the Explainable AI approach (Nazar et al., 2021) is reviewed and explained; then in the section 4 the requirements of the future ES are listed. Particularly interesting for the respect for persons principle are the following requirements (per each requirement we insert only the code and the description, referring to the section 2.5.4 of the D5.1 for all other details):</i></p> <p>Code: ES-13</p> <p>Title: ES - Guided steps</p> <p><i>The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.</i></p> <p><i>Each task will be categorized and will allow to use metadata information for better future recommendations.</i></p> <p>Code: ES-15</p> <p>Title: Communicate with patients at key times</p> <p><i>The system shall ensure communication with patients at key times.</i></p> <p>Code: DAN-4</p> <p>Title: Support ES- Guided steps</p>

Requirement	Implementation
	<p>The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.</p> <p>Code: DAN-5 Title: Recommend analyses' types The Data Analytics Component shall retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. Next, the user will have the capability via the UI to choose which statistical function should be applied to the data, depending on the available ones based on the input data. This functionality will be provided to the user at the stage of data distribution (DAN-14), analysing the data (DAN-1), and Exploratory Data Analysis (DAN-12).</p> <p>Code: DAN-6 Title: Selection of cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria The system shall allow to select cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria (upon performing an analysis, select whom you will study based on x, y, z criteria).</p> <p>Code: DAN-11 Title: Generation of a report as output The Data Analytics Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. Next, at each stage of applying algorithms for analysing and processing the data, the Data Analytics Component should be able to save which programming language, i.e., Python, MATLAB, R, etc. and library, i.e., SciPy, Nilearn, MNE, etc. was used for conducting the respective experiments. Finally, after the user has completed all the analyses, the system shall be able to export a file, which will include the programming language and the libraries used for each specific analysis.</p> <p>Code: AI-7 Title: Support ES - Guided steps The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.</p>

5.2 NON MALEFICENCE

Table 10: Desktop assessment for the PUC2 of the non-maleficence requirements

Requirement	Implementation
Personal data of participants must be protected to avoid any possible inappropriate use	<p>In the deliverable 5.1 section 4.1 is described the anonymisation module and the corresponding requirements:</p> <p>Code: Code: AM-1</p>

Requirement	Implementation
and any damage deriving from it	<p><i>Title: Local RWD anonymisation</i></p> <p>The Anonymisation module is one of the modules pluggable into the Local back end. It will allow to use a local script/app/executable for automatically anonymising/defacing/etc. local RWD before they are uploaded in the system.</p> <p><i>Code: Code AM-3</i></p> <p><i>Title: Communicate with patients at key times</i></p> <p>Once anonymised, the module will send the data to the cloud platform for analytical purposes.</p>

As it is evident from the above requirements and from the figure below and the description present in the D4.1 section 5.2.2, the data are anonymized BEFORE being put into the system, avoiding in this way any risks regarding personal data protection (it's not possible to trace back to the single participant).

Figure 3: data anonymisation

The de-personalization process is described both in D5.1 section 5.2.2 and in the D2.3, section 4.3. For maximum security, each clinic has its de-personalization module, so that personal data do not have to be transferred with all the connected risks.

Requirement **Implementation**

Figure 4: de-personalization process

<p><i>The clinicians and all other healthcare professionals who will use the platform will be adequately trained. They must be able to use the platform and to understand its outputs</i></p>	<p><i>The researchers participating in the MES-CoBraD research are all skilled and expert researchers, their curricula have been assessed and are accessible in the DOA. As per the training that will be done to make them acquainted with the platform. Feedback from platform users (researchers, clinicians) will be gathered so as to furtherly improve usability and any identified drawbacks. Dedicated training sections are foreseen.</i></p> <p><i>Please also refer to the section 6 below on this.</i></p>
<p><i>The validity of the outputs of the platform will be adequately tested and verified, by scientifically validated means</i></p>	<p><i>The software produced according with the requirements of D5.1 will be validated according to the framework described in the D8.2, D4.2-D4.6 and the description of validation for the Expert System is in the DoA (see e.g., PUC1-PUC4 description) . The following KPI describes how the evaluation of accuracy will be done: # of comparisons on accuracy between expert PO analyses offline and with use of online modules within CoBraD. For more details on this please see the section 6.</i></p>
<p><i>The system must be protected from cyber-attacks and data breaches. A recovery plan is in place in case of system failure or damage or breach</i></p>	<p><i>See data management plan (D2.2) Annex VII (Cybersecurity Plan)</i></p>
<p><i>Measures should be taken to protect the patient/doctor relationship and avoid the risk of depersonalization of care and (from the clinician side) of depriving of sense the medical profession</i></p>	<p><i>On this point, please see the section 6.</i></p>

5.3 JUSTICE

Table 11: Desktop assessment for the PUC2 of the Justice requirements

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Requirement	Implementation
<p>Defining procedures and mitigation actions to avoid the misuse of the MES-CoBraD platform (for example to profile people for insurance purposes)</p>	<p>This is a big issue because a tool like the MES-CoBraD platform could be used to ameliorate the knowledge on complex brain diseases and as a consequence the life of many people but immediately do come to mind also potential misuses of such a powerful tool, for example the possibility of spotting people more at risk of developing a brain illness could be used by insurance companies or by human resources for far from clear purposes. Being the PUC2 concerned only with the analysis of the data and with the setting of the AI module, this requirement (which has already been discussed in D2.3 section 2.4) can be only partially addressed here, but certainly we can pinpoint the risk and start to think about some possible mitigation actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU legislation allows mass screening and surveillance for reasons of public safety. What it's illegal is the purpose of the use of the data, according to the GDPR you cannot use the data and the inferences made to discriminate or damage the individuals. So, since whoever uses the platform should also be obliged to use it respecting what is prescribed by EU laws and regulations, this would represent a safeguard against possible such misuses (it would not be possible to LEGALLY use the system in such a way) • All systems of this kind (capable of analyzing personal data and with access to sensitive data) present a risk of being used for social scoring purposes. Thanks to the de-personalization operations performed on data this should not be possible with MES-CoBraD because the individual cannot be traced back starting from the data available in MES-CoBraD. • All the details on the data management plan and data protection can be found in D2.2 (data management plan)
<p>Any effort is made to avoid the presence of algorithmic biases and the generation of misdiagnosis or under diagnosis at scale and that appropriate debiasing techniques are applied</p>	<p>Random and representative sampling is pursued. Special emphasis is placed on including vulnerable and underserved populations. External validation is outlined for several analyses, especially the Expert System (see PUC4 description and D4.2-D4.6)</p>
<p>Health personnel or researchers are not discriminated as a result of their inability to use MES-CoBraD</p>	<p>See section 6 on this</p>
<p>It's clear how responsibility and legal liability would be allocated, there are procedures to request redress, and they are known to participants</p>	<p>This is a theme object of a strong debate. The fact that, as it is specified for example in D6.1 section 2.4.5, the consortium decided to adopt the explainable AI approach (something which solves the opacity problem) indicates that the opacity of the system's outputs will be avoided and that any effort will be made to ensure accountability. In any case, the harmonized acquisition protocol follows real-world standard of care rules that are combined and it's not clear whether the inclusion of an AI expert system (which is a guide to clinicians, providing information, not a decision maker) effectively changes the</p>

Requirement	Implementation
	<i>accountability relationship between doctor and patient. But on this topic please see also the section 6, where emerges that in fact this difference in accountability (with and without ES) is not perceived by clinical partners)</i>

6 ANALYSIS OF THE SELF ASSESSMENT

The self-assessment was carried out starting with the distribution among clinical and technical partners of an ethical questionnaire on issues that may arise both from PUC1 and PUC2.

We divided the questionnaire in four sections, that mirrored the four ethical principles on the basis of which we outlined the ethical requirements: “respect for persons” (furtherly divided into “autonomy” and “respect”), “beneficence”, “non-maleficence” and “justice”. We didn’t include in the questionnaire all the ethical requirements, but rather we tried to extract from the requirements some questions that we thought particularly interesting in the context of MES-CoBraD and to which we couldn’t locate satisfying answers in the available documentation. Some questions are truly speculative in nature and were necessary to open a line of discussion and self-reflexion internal to the consortium on some topics, that for obvious reasons could not be fully solved here.

In the following sections, for each area we will briefly summarize the main outcomes, by using a table with the answers we received to each question (most of the questions were open).

6.1 DISCUSSION OF THE ANSWERS

6.1.1 RESPECT FOR PERSONS

The principle of the respect for persons is a subtle one, because it incorporates obvious and in certain cases mandatory requirements (for instance the obligation to inform the patient of all the risks and burdens he/she may face participating in the research) but as we mentioned before it can also be interpreted, giving place to a pronounced variability. This is exactly what happened with the questionnaire we submitted: the first thing that is evident is that some partners interpreted it in a strict way while others more extensively, trying to go beyond what is prescribed by law. This finding is an interesting “side-effect” of the ethics evaluation of the PUCs, since it highlights differences in healthcare approaches and foster a reflexion to what it really means the principle of respect for persons (but the same applies also to the other principles) when put into practice.

So, for instance, as far as the first question, while everyone said that they inform the patients about the risks and/or advantages through an information sheet, some partners go beyond and not only they provide the prospect participants with a load of written material but they also engage with them in an in-depth interview (80% of the answers) and other go further giving the possibility to patients to discuss the topic thoroughly with a project partner.

The situation is similar for the question on research outcomes updates: while all the partners update the participants on the outcomes of the research, the level of engagement and personalisation in this activity varies greatly, going from sending emails to inviting participants to an open day dedicated to disclosing the research results and a continuous personalized review.

The procedure to abandon the study is quite simple but not always codified or explicitly described to participants. In any case no formal declaration or signature is necessary, it suffices an email, a telephone call or a verbal declaration, at any point of the study.

On the rest of the questions related to the respect for persons section there was wide uniformity, so that all partners answered in the same way to the questions related to the availability of a direct contact with the researchers (yes) and to the questions aimed at understanding how the introduction of MES-CoBraD might change the relationship patient/doctor (no).

As far as the accountability of the doctor/clinician, all partners answered that the outcomes of MES-CoBraD will always be mediated by a human doctor, so in their view the ES should be considered only a diagnostic aid (in the same way as for example the MR imaging is) not hindering in any way neither the

accountability nor the autonomy of the clinicians.

Furthermore, both from the partners answers and from the desktop assessment, it emerged that the system will have a way to “explain” its outputs and that the UI is specifically made with the intention of making the outputs of the system understandable also to non-technical personnel, avoiding the “black-box” effect. Also, on these aspects (responsibility, accountability, autonomy) a more in-depth investigation would be necessary during the next project months to clarify if the autonomy and accountability of the individual is not really influenced by the system. This point will be further investigated in the deliverable D3.9 (ETHAI model).

Table 12: Summary and discussion of the answers to the Respect for persons section of the questionnaire

Question	Summary of the answers
<i>Through what means are the possible risks and/or advantages of participating in research explained to patients?</i>	<i>All the partners will inform participants through an information sheet. The majority of the partners will use also dedicated interviews and will provide information also with the consent form. Some partners will provide also other kind of material (pamphlets, commercials, in-depth discussion)</i>
<i>Will the research participants be updated and/or informed of the results/outcomes of the research? If yes, through what means?</i>	<i>All partners answered that the participants will be updated and/or informed by means of a periodic conversation with a researcher. Other means of information (but not adopted by everyone) will be emails and website. One partner intends to organize an open day for a full disclosure of research results.</i>
<i>What is the procedure the participant has to follow in order to abandon the study?</i>	<i>All partners answered that participants can abandon at any time without giving any justification. The procedures that each one indicated are all different but converge on the fact that there is no formalized procedure, nor necessity of a declaration or signature</i>
<i>Do the participants in the research have the possibility to directly address the clinicians with questions and/or information requests?</i>	<i>All the clinical partners answered that there is such a possibility</i>
<i>Does the algorithm have a system for reporting/explaining its outputs? Will the explanations be understandable also by patients or will the clinicians explain them?</i>	<i>The partners said that – in agreement with the requirement on explainable AI - the system has a reporting and analytics tool that can give accurate results and explain the output of all the workflows that were followed, based on the input values. The patients will get a dedicated time with a researcher who will explain to them the output of the system. The patients will not be able to access directly to the output of the system.</i>
<i>How is the accountability of diagnoses and decisions taken with the help of MES-CoBraD guaranteed? Is the clinician always responsible as he/she is when no AI is involved?</i>	<i>The partners said that there is no difference in this with respect to the usual clinical practice: the clinician is always responsible, the Expert System will only act as a medical Decision Support System, giving estimated guidance but leaving any decision to the human clinician</i>
<i>In your opinion there may exist the risk that the autonomy of clinician's judgment is hindered while using the MES-CoBraD system?</i>	<i>6 partners out of 8 who answered to this question said that there is no risk with respect to the clinician's autonomy. However, two partners answered that there may be such a risk</i>

Question	Summary of the answers
<p>- 1. How the clinician and the Expert System will interact and communicate with each other?</p> <p>- 2. Will the system output diagnostic inferences or will it constitute only an information database for the clinician?</p>	<p>The partners agree that the clinician – through a dedicated web interface – will have to feed to the system he data he/she considers relevant for the diagnosis and choose the types of analysis of these data. He/she will also be able to access existing data or other information available into the platform. The system will output data analysis and hypothesis testing that the clinician may use if he/she decides to</p>
<p>Are there any mechanisms for the patients and/or for the clinicians to contest or rectify AI-enabled decisions? How can the patient and/or the clinician access the data on which a certain decision is based?</p>	<p>Each analysis is enriched with the underneath data. Basing on them, the clinician can understand the reason of a given result and, eventually, contest or rectify it. Quite interesting is that the system will have a module for the clinician or the patient to give a contribution or a different opinion that can be considered on the next version of the software update, so the system not only provides “justification” of its suggestions but can also evolve thanks to the interaction with users and patients</p>
<p>Is there the intention to enable MES-CoBraD to take autonomous decisions or will it always be mediated by a human?</p>	<p>The decisions will always be taken by human clinicians, no autonomous decisions will be delegated to the system</p>

6.1.2 BENEFICENCE

According to the Oviedo Convention (Treaty No.164, 1997), participation in research should be beneficial to the single participant or – in the case of biomedical research – to the same class of people (meaning people with the same disease or in the same condition of the participant). The way in which MES-CoBraD research will benefit the society as a whole or classes of people is quite evident, being its aim a significant improvement of diagnosis and care. At the level of the single participant the benefits are less evident but are nonetheless present, as it’s clear from the following answers, lying mainly in the access to extremely in-depth analyses and health conditions evaluation, as well as in the discovery of previously unknown comorbidities and undiagnosed medical conditions. In any case it results that the burdens are not such to overcome the possible benefits, even at individual level.

Table 13: Summary and discussion of the Beneficence section of the questionnaire

Question	Summary of the answers
<p>Please explain how the participation in the research is beneficial to the single participant</p>	<p>Participants receive a comprehensive real world multi modal assessment that is typically not within reach for free in standard healthcare. The advancement in diagnosis and treatment can benefit them either directly, by taking advantage of a better informed clinician who treat them while using MES-CoBraD, and indirectly by advancing the medical field that affects them. The contribution of each single patient would help the clinicians to make diagnoses of diseases in their prodromal phase and intervene on them earlier, allowing the development of clinical trials aimed at modifying the course of the disease and thereby reducing the degree of disability and the significant investment of energy, time and money that this</p>

Question	Summary of the answers
	<i>entails for family members, companies and the state.</i>
<i>During the course of a clinical study, previously undiagnosed medical conditions unrelated to the aims of the study are sometimes discovered. These are referred to as ‘incidental findings’. Do you have an incidental finding policy? If not, which measures are taken in case a comorbidity or another illness is discovered thanks to the research activities?</i>	<i>All project sites do have an incidental findings policy. In all project sites during the course of research Brain (head) MRI done in the course of the prospective data collection are reviewed by a board certified radiologists for unrelated pathology (neck cancers, mouth lesions). Similarly done for EEG tests (reviewed by epileptologists). If something is discovered the patient is contacted for consultation and referral to the appropriate specialist if necessary. In one case the hospital assumes responsibility for the medical care and expenses incurred for incidental findings</i>

6.1.3 NON MALEFICENCE

Possible sources of maleficence occurring to the patients as a result of their participation in the research or (when the platform will be operational) as a result of them being treated with the help of MES-CoBraD were analysed.

Three possible categories of factors that may cause a damage and that are different from the possible damages/burdens that may occur as a side effect of research (which are detailed in the consent form and in the information sheet) were taken into account:

- Damages due to the presence of the AI (a malfunctioning of the system - for technical but also for algorithmic or human reasons - causing a wrong diagnosis and/or the loss of the personalised and unique relationship doctor/patient (“depersonalisation of care”) because of the partial automatization of the diagnostic process)
- Data breach or loss
- Indirect, psychological damages to vulnerable persons due to a lack of attention and safeguards.

From the answers that the partners gave, it’s quite evident that measures such as the presence of a risk assessment document or of a safety case are known and understood. Moreover, other questions concerning (i) the relationship between the doctor and the patient, (ii) how it is modified by the introduction of the AI, (iii) the risk that the system returns wrong diagnoses for any reason (bad design, biases, system malfunctioning) are not perceived as issues. This is a useful finding, because we can derive ethics action items for the project’s prosecution. In general, it seems that the presence of an AI is not problematised from an ethical or clinical point of view and it is perceived as a tool supporting the clinicians.

Table 14: Summary and discussion of the Non-Maleficence section of the questionnaire

Question	Summary of the answers
<i>Do you have a risk assessment document? Are there any mitigation strategies for the highlighted risks?</i>	<i>The partners answered affirmatively</i>
<i>How are the rights of the vulnerable persons safeguarded? Which additional safeguards are put in place (e.g., in case of children or of mentally impaired persons)?</i>	<i>The protection measure on which all partners agree is the presence during the recruitment procedure of a family member, a caregiver or a legal tutor. Some partners do provide further measures, such as a capacity interview with a psychiatrist. Only one partner does recruits children.</i>

Question	Summary of the answers
<p>Are there established procedures to train the clinicians/researchers who will use the platform?</p>	<p>Here only two partners answered affirmatively (while 3 answered no and 4 don't know). These should make an alarm bell ring, because it's of the utmost importance – to avoid human error – that the people who is going to use the platform be adequately trained.</p>
<p>How is the risk of depersonalisation of care avoided? Is there the risk that the relationship between the clinician and the patient is modified as an effect of using the MES-CoBraD system?</p>	<p>To this question each partner answered differently (as it was expectable, since it's a speculative question) but two pointed out that the big problem in the depersonalization of care is not the technology used, but the process which is undergoing and that leads to a progressive loss of the individual relationship doctor/patient. Technology (and which technology) is only a part of a bigger problem.</p>
<p>How is the security of the system ensured? Indicate whether there is a cybersecurity plan to protect data from external attacks and/or a plan to recover data in case of loss or theft</p>	<p>The data are stored in the data lake that is hosted in an already existing, well tested and secure infrastructure in the Cloud. Several penetration tests and vulnerability assessments have been executed in the past by the infrastructure owner so the probability of a data leak or breach is very low.</p> <p>In any case, the data stored in the data lake are depersonalised so the identity of the patients will always be protected.</p> <p>Moreover, periodic backups are done (once per week) so, in case of data loss, they can be restored quite quickly. Risk management procedures will be put into place to secure the system against cybersecurity threats, based on the ISO 27001 standard for Information Security Management</p>
<p>Are there established procedures to request redress? If yes please specify</p>	<p>The partners answered no or don't know to this question. These procedures apply in case of medical negligence, so on the one hand we can assume that procedures to request redress in case of MES-CoBraD research or usage are the same that in usual clinical practice, from the other hand probably it would be necessary to focus on whether the introduction of AI in the process makes enhanced or modified procedures necessary.</p>
<p>Does a safety case exist and will it be provided to the patient?</p>	<p>Two partners answered affirmatively, other said that they don't know or they don't understand the question</p>
<p>Is understandability to non-technical personnel (e.g. health personnel) guaranteed? How?</p>	<p>The whole system is addressed to non-technical personnel. The user interface and the usage of Expert System is designed to be user friendly and addressed to non-technical users. Documentation, Explainable AI, and metadata management, for both the data and their processing is foreseen for all interaction with prosomal information throughout the platform.</p>
<p>Inconclusive evidence: are there defined procedures that grant the patient against the possibility of algorithmic error? How will be the effectiveness of MES-CoBraD results proven/verified? (With reference to the following KPI: # of comparisons on accuracy between</p>	<p>Some partners underlined the fact that diagnoses are probabilistic and always mediated by humans. Comparative analyses will be peer reviewed and published in respectable scientific journals and conferences. The specific details of the validation different methods that will be used are defined by the researchers involved in them and reviewed by the scientific community. In any case, one partner pointed out that PUC4 has this goal. the outline of the assessment is in the DoA.</p>

Question	Summary of the answers
expert PO analyses offline and with use of online modules within CoBraD ≥ 3)	

6.1.4 JUSTICE

With this battery of questions, the questionnaire investigates possible negative implications for social justice derived by the MES-CoBraD expert system usage. The analysis focused in particular on group selection and on the possible presence of biases due to an incorrect group composition and consequently on the data sets used for training the algorithm. We also tried to draw the partner's attention on possible misuses of the platform such as profiling, social scoring, restricting access to healthcare in consequence of certain behaviours, etc.

Table 15: Summary and discussion of the answers to the Justice section of the questionnaire

Question	Summary of the answers
<p>A correct group composition is fundamental to avoid biases, especially when AI and machine learning are involved. Please state whether you are reaching the KPIs relative to the group composition stated into the DOA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant female to male ratio \approx (range 0.8 – 1.2) % of participants belonging to an ethnic, socioeconomic, or gender minority $\geq 10\%$ Congruence of participant socioeconomic background to respective community ≥ 0.7 	<p>Partners reported a difficulty in reaching the KPIs because of the still small number of people recruited and because (one partner) "gender minority advocacy groups approached were "not interested in participating in this research" because it was outside their scope of interest". Despite that, gender minority participants participate in the project individually, but are not engaged through advocacy organizations. One partner (KCL) did not start the recruitment yet. Please also refer to the D8.4 deliverable for more information on group composition status in the different POs.</p>
<p>Please state the criteria (inclusion and exclusion) according to which you selected the participants to the research</p>	<p>One partner answered that there are no special criteria (anyone who comes to the clinic providing the consent form and has a related disease), two referred to the IRB and to a list of criteria to be uploaded and one inserted its selection and exclusion criteria. Obviously, it is not part of an ethical assessment to evaluate the validity of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, but the absence of criteria instead it's questionable, since as we mentioned before a correct group selection has a strong influence also on social justice matters.</p>
<p>In your opinion does the possibility of misuse and/or abuse of the MES-CoBraD platform exist (e.g. profiling, discrimination, etc)? If yes, what procedures have been</p>	<p>The majority of the partners does not have a definite opinion on this, also because the platform is not available still. Two partners who work on the technical WPs answered that the possibility of misuse/abuse of the MES-CoBraD platform are minimized through specific measures that include the</p>

Question	Summary of the answers
<i>enforced to avoid that?</i>	<p>following:</p> <p>Data anonymization, access control, user identification and encryption capabilities in order to avoid unauthorized accesses and data abuses. Also, Explainable AI, and debiasing methods are foreseen</p>
<i>Presence of biases: are there any tests to monitor the presence of bias in the execution of the algorithm and are debiasing mechanisms foreseen (with particular reference to historical, representation, measurement, aggregation and evaluation biases)? Could there be racial and/or sex and gender biases involuntarily built into the algorithm? How is it avoided the risk of misdiagnosis or missed diagnosis at scale?</i>	<p>The majority of partners answered that they don't know or that there are no debiasing mechanisms yet. Two partners answered that this will depend on how classifiers and other functions are developed by the researchers. these will be cross-validated on external samples, as per PUC4. Anyway, since bias can be detected by understanding the data source, the system can only ensure that this dataset is not overprocessed. The system may allow the removal of outliers and add minimum to none filters, especially on subset and gender selection. As for the AI, during the model generation on a train dataset, the algorithm will not focus too much on the dataset itself and will not make a generalized decision in order to keep a balance between over train and underfitting the test dataset. Debiasing procedures from the algorithm are not presented now.</p>
<i>Do you believe that a system like MES-CoBraD could have negative implications for social justice, inadvertently undermining people's health, or well-being, or increasing disparities in access to social and health service structures? Please explain your answer (either negative or positive)</i>	<p>The majority of the partners answered that MesCoBraD would be expected to have positive impact in increasing the diagnostic accuracy and reducing the time for diagnosis and treatment and that couldn't have negative implications for social justice, as it will be used as just supplementary source of information for a clinician. Two however pointed out that the risk of misuse (e.g., to prognose health for financial/insurance reasons) exists.</p>
<i>Could MES-CoBraD represent a source of discrimination for clinicians or a barrier (meaning that for some reason, clinicians do not manage to use it)?</i>	<p>Some partners here reported that a risk may exist due to the costs of implementation and/or training. Otherwise, it is believed that MES-CoBraD will not represent a source of discrimination for researchers, the plans being that it will be made available to anyone wanting to use it</p>
<i>Could MES-CoBraD worsen the already existing inequalities in access to health care? E.g. favouring certain groups over other ones in access to diagnosis/care? Or "blaming" certain groups of people for their behaviour? How do you plan to avoid this possibility?</i>	<p>Partners do not see this risk, except for reasons due to costs. If they see the risk, they think that it's a discrimination made on purpose and that it is fully avoidable ("MES-CoBraD is not foreseen to be used directly for informing policy, nor does it use policy or other mechanisms to prioritise diagnosis or treatment for specific groups. It's decision criteria are solely clinical.")</p>

7 COMPARISON BETWEEN DESKTOP AND SELF ASSESSMENT

In general, no meaningful differences emerged confronting what came out from the desktop assessment with the answers to the questionnaire. The main comparison results were rather the clarification through the self-assessment of some points not completely clear from the deliverables (such as for instance the information procedures or the management of vulnerable individuals), as well as the update of some requirements (such as for instance the KPIs on selection criteria).

In conclusion, the comparison results in a good correspondence between what is declared in the DOA and in the deliverables we examined and what is actually being done.

However, some points are still not clear to partners, due to the fact that they did not yet have the possibility to see the whole integrated platform working. But since the project is still in progress and two PUCs are still in their initial phase, this could be expectable.

As far as the ethics concerns, although they have been thematized and discussed in the related deliverables (mostly those related to the application of AI to healthcare) they have not been completely incorporated into the platform yet. With the caveat that the implementation phase of one of the core system components, the ES, is really not yet mature, there is still ample room to introduce all the elements that the consortium deems necessary. The assessment will be conducted during the rest of the project, where the components will be enough mature to be analysed. It will be reported in v2 of this deliverable.

8 DATA PROTECTION EVALUATION OF PUC1 AND PUC2

In order to ensure accountability of the research during the project, all partners in the project have nominated a Data Protection Officer and signed a compliance statement concerning their obligations towards national and EU legislation, with regards to the processing of data carried at their institution's premises.

The processing activities during the research performed at the MES-CoBraD platform, are designed by default, to operate in a pseudonymised manner and under need-to know protocols. An in deep analysis of the legal and ethical safeguards on the processing of personal data in MES-CoBraD is provided in D2.3 Ethical and Regulatory Framework (section 4) and D2.2 Data Management Plan v1.

To ensure that processing activities derived from PUC1 and PUC2 are respectful with the principles of and obligations of data protection the following actions have been adopted or are being developed by the consortium:

Table 16 PUCs data protection assessment

Document/ Action	Reference of relevant deliverable
De-personalisation of data: Description of the anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques used by the project description of the	Data Management Plan subsection 2.5.2. See also D.2.3 Ethical and Regulatory Framework subsection 4.3 and D.5.1 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security, for a technical description of the envisaged measures
Data processing consortium policy:	D2.2 Data Management Plan Annex V
Data Subject Requests Protocol: a document explaining how data subject requests would be handled by the partners.	D2.2 Data Management Plan Annex VI
Data Protection Notice regarding personal data processing at the MES-CoBraD Platform: A brief explanation in lay man terms on the main aspects of the data processing activities in MES-CoBraD.	D2,2 Data Management Plan Annex VIII
Cybersecurity policy: A description of the technical and organisational measures, including security measures and protocols that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants processed during MES-CoBraD.	D.2.3 Ethical and Regulatory Framework section 4 and its future iteration D.2.9, as well as D2.2 Data Management Plan Annex VII
Data transfers record: Identification and when relevant, confirmation that personal data transfers from EU to non-EU countries are performed in accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.	D2.3 section 4 section 4.10 and Data Management Plan section 2.5.3.

9 CONCLUSION

PUC1 and PUC2 represent a key part of the project and one that may raise ethics and legal challenges, being concerned with the recruitment of human participants, the gathering of real-world data and the subsequent management of those data with advanced analytics and machine learning tools.

The assessment carried out in this first part of the project was conducted mainly through the analysis of both the available documentation on the PUCs and the answers to the ethics questionnaire submitted to partners. The picture that emerges is generally good, with some improvement areas or points to be further investigated, mostly in the light of the progress of the project especially for what concerns the implementation of the Expert System and the related ethics principles (accountability, explainability, autonomy).

As per the data protection evaluation, as we mentioned in the section 8 the main points are already present in the deliverables D2.2 (data management plan) and D2.3 (legal and ethical framework), but the main point to be paid attention to lies on the kind of de-personalization that each partner will choose to perform (anonymization or pseudonymization). In any case all the partners signed a declaration of compliance with the requirements of the GDPR (cfr D2.3 section 4.9.2).

The next sections will highlight the main assessment outcomes and the topics to be further examined as well as some possible areas for improvement that may be considered in the future project months.

In the following table we recap quickly the main findings and the related actions (of which you will find an extended version in the subsections below):

Table 17: PUCs ethical and legal assessment recap

Principle	Assessment	Proposed Actions
Respect for Persons	<i>The Autonomy requirements are all respected and satisfied, both by PUC1 and PUC2, but the matter of the autonomy of researchers with respect to the ES is left open as it appears to not be perceived as a problem. If we move to the Respect requirements, an opportunity for reflection may be represented by the set of requirements that pertain to the empathy field (feelings, sensations, point of views of participants) and to the protection of vulnerable people</i>	Dedicate an internal focus group to the matter of the relationship between clinicians and ES. Improve the UATs and start an internal reflection with partners on how to answer to this challenge by developing common rules (that reflect a broader vision of the Respect principle) to manage the participants, including the vulnerable ones.
Beneficence	There are two levels of “Beneficence”, the individual and the societal one. MES-CoBraD research satisfies both, because it results potentially beneficial for the single participant but also for the society as a whole. This is true both for PUC1 (partners recruitment and RWD gathering) and for the PUC2 (advanced analytics).	It might surely be interesting, and in fact it will be one of the objects of WP4 work group Ethics, Policy and Society, to thoroughly understand and assess the impacts that MES-CoBraD may have on society and on healthcare systems.
Non Maleficence	Risks and Benefits are commiserated and no serious	For the matter of autonomy/liability, it might be interesting to open an

Principle	Assessment	Proposed Actions
	<p>damage may occur as a direct result of the research. Personal data of participants is correctly managed and protected. Both PUC1 and PUC2 satisfy the requirements deriving from the Non Maleficence principle. However, especially for PUC2 and in general for the ES component, which is not yet complete, some challenges remain open, especially those pertaining to accountability and to the training procedures necessary in order to learn how to use the platform</p>	<p>internal reflection with a mixed group of clinicians, engineers and philosophers, to understand if this is really not perceived as a problem by clinicians and if there is a common approach by all the PUCs POs. With respect to training, it will probably be necessary to organize internal discussions at each PO level to let all the people involved to acquire the necessary competencies.</p>
Justice	<p>Since this principles contains some requirements (i.e. those about group composition and related biases) whose respect is, due to their nature, dynamic and in evolution, we may say that both PUC1 and PUC2 are adopting a correct stance with respect to this principle, with the definitive satisfaction of each requirement changing over time but going in the right direction. In particular the group composition and the absence of biases requirements are difficult to assess at this stage, but PUCs POs are taking all the necessary actions in order to respect them.</p>	<p>Identify together with all the PUCs POs the most challenging group composition KPIs and if necessary find appropriate mitigation actions.</p>
Research Safety and Mutual Duty of Care	<p>Both from the desktop assessment and from the self-assessment (the ethical questionnaire and the internal sex and gender questionnaire) it is clear that the different organizations part of the MES-CoBraD Consortium represent an excellent work environment from the point of view of the Research Safety principle. Possible areas of improvement could be identified in the area of the Mutual Duty of Care principle, but possible mitigation actions are already foreseen.</p>	<p>Modify the UATs to include a more extensive participants feedback; together with partners start an internal reflection on the best way to safeguard vulnerable people (given that the Consortium already satisfies the normative requirements on this) and in general on whether something else can be done to make patients feel more comfortable and cared for.</p>
Open Science	<p>From the assessment it results that MES-CoBraD consortium fully adheres and respects the Open Science principle and requirements</p>	<p>Continue to explore new ways to engage and involve citizens and researchers from other fields (citizen science)</p>

9.1 RESPECT FOR PERSONS

Both PUC1 and PUC2 comply with the main requirements for this principle. We noticed that the respect for persons is interpreted mainly as respect for autonomy, and in particular as compliance with the information rights of the participants (both before and during the participation and after it ends). Following the approach of (Kraft et al., 2020) we suggest a different approach, based on a broader interpretation of the respect principles that includes further elements such as for instance the way in which researchers talk to patients and approach them, the way participants' feedback, opinions and sensations are valued and respected, the procedures with which vulnerable patients are managed.

In particular we suggest that:

- In the UAT, patients are also asked feedback about the way they felt during the recruitment and research phase, the way they have been approached, etc.
- The clinical partners, with the support and aid of CEL, further discuss common rules to manage the participants based on this broader sense of respect and that they make sure it is applied (offering to researchers and clinicians dedicated training and written materials). This could be an interesting outcome also for other projects that do research with humans, in particular with vulnerable or fragile people.
- As per the management of vulnerable persons (see D2.6 for a detailed description of the procedures adopted by each partner), we suggest to enhance it by taking into account different kinds of vulnerability and associated problematic areas (again working together scientific and humanistic partners). As for the majority of clinical studies (even in other projects), protecting vulnerable participants in MES-CoBraD mostly focuses on the matter of consent (and thus of autonomy). However, specific safeguards for vulnerable persons would be useful. Again, this might constitute a valuable help also for other projects where research with humans is necessary.

9.2 PARTICIPANTS FREEDOM AND NON-DISCRIMINATION

The requirements regarding the correctly informed participation of participants are definitely respected: all partners provide detailed information sheets and consent forms to participants, but more than this they engage the prospect participants in personalized interviews, screenings, occasions of discussion and clarification; they also give the participants a direct contact of a trained researcher should they have any question.

The slight challenging areas here do emerge with respect to the recruitment criteria and the consequential group composition.

To obtain results that are not biased (something which may happen if for example a certain group, e.g., black women, is under or over represented), it's very important to aim at a group composition that not only includes people with the diseases object of the research but also that is representative of certain factors that could have an impact or an effect on those diseases (just to make an example, gender is surely one of these factors). This approach is stated in the DOA as well as in the project manual (D3.1 and D3.2) and is reflected in the PUC1 KPIs.

First of all, from the questionnaire it emerged that not all the partners are reaching the KPIs relative to the group composition. On the other hand, there are objective issues related to the patients recruitment, such as for instance the difficulty to reach some categories of patients (see D2.6 for the inclusion/exclusion criteria of each partner).

- We suggest that internal discussions are organised on this issue to identify the most challenging KPIs as well as the main factors that determine the difficulty in reaching them, with the aim of finding appropriate mitigation measures.
- Then, potential remediation actions should be planned and put in place in case of KPIs yet not

reachable.

9.3 AI APPLIED TO HEALTHCARE

At the moment of the writing of this deliverable, artificial intelligence and machine learning modules have not been developed yet, and consequently it has not been possible for anyone to fully experiment the platform potentialities as well as the AI related potential problematic areas.

However, since the description of the characteristics and aims of the PUC2 do include both artificial intelligence and machine learning, we deemed that these areas should have been part of our assessment.

Therefore, we analysed the requirements and we also asked dedicated questions to the partners, both technical and clinical, with the following outcome: while from the desktop assessment it's evident that there has been a debate and reflexion on these aspects related to AI, from the questionnaire it seems that the clinical partners at the moment do not consider the presence of AI something to be problematised or that may constitute a threat or may introduce radical differences in the actual healthcare process. They seem to consider AI as some sort of highly sophisticated tool that helps the clinician in his/her work in the same way as other tools do, such as for instance the magnetic resonance or the rx.

This is an interesting finding that should be taken into account. There are of course "objective" potential issues (Schiff & Borenstein, 2019) (for instance the presence of biases or the explainability of AI mechanisms) that are perceived as challenges and faced. But there are other, more subtle issues, like the autonomy of the researcher/clinician, or the potential discrimination arising from the adoption of an AI based system, that are not considered critical.

- We suggest that later on, when the platform is more mature, we dedicate to this issue an internal focus group with clinicians involved in the project making use of the Expert System, to see if their perception has changed. Moreover, we suggest to re-submit to the partners the ethics questionnaire questions dedicated to AI and ML. The results of this further analysis will find place in the D3.9 (ETHAI model) and in the v2 of this deliverable, that will concern the PUCs #3 and #4.

More in detail, while the requirements regarding the transparency and the explainability have been satisfied, at least in the design (requirements) phase, the human agency and oversight is not considered an issue since the clinician will have to interpret and to filter the outputs of the system and will always have the last word on any diagnosis.

Moreover, since further requirements (i.e., the presence of debiasing procedures and the trustability) will be faced and dealt with in the next project phases, they are not completely satisfied yet. In particular, we think that the absence (at the moment) of debiasing procedures and the evaluation of the accuracy and validity of MES-CoBraD outputs need further investigation. Despite both are currently known and their thematization planned, they are not completely defined and accounted for yet.

We suggest:

- To form a mixed work-group in WP4 (with clinical, technical and humanistic partners) to discuss the matter of possible biases and related debiasing procedures and in general the problems of AI applied to healthcare in the context of MES-CoBraD.
- To dedicate the same work group to the matter of validation of MES-CoBraD diagnoses, defining a process through which the validation happens with reference to the following PUC2 KPI: *# of comparisons on accuracy between expert PO analyses offline and with use of online modules within CoBraD* ≥ 3 .

Slightly different is the situation regarding the possible discrimination issues and the potential problems deriving from the (presence or absence of) skills of the clinicians that will have to use the platform. These

are known and taken into account by the consortium but still not completely solved.

- We propose that the partners do elaborate clear and well-defined procedures on the matter and that internal discussions are organized at each PO level to make sure that all the people using MES-CoBraD acquire the necessary skills and competences.

With respect to the ethics of care and to how the relationship doctor/patient and the role of trained healthcare professionals may change as a consequence of the adoption of a system like MES-CoBraD, one of the WP4 workgroups (Ethics, Policy, Society Workgroup) is currently working on it. The same is for the impacts on the healthcare systems considered globally (could MES-CoBraD worsen inequalities? Or on the contrary it may be expectable that it has have positive effects on social justice?).

We think that mixed workgroups (WP4) might really make the difference in a complex project like MES-CoBraD, where multiple competencies must converge to attain a product that not only works but that is also acceptable from an ethical point of view.

Wanting to respect the open science principles, MES-CoBraD will make its results and its datasets available also to researchers not participating to the project. We think that also ethics and legal issues and challenges, and the possible solutions found by the members of the consortium, could be part of this common knowledge, to be shared and made available for the entire scientific community.

To sum up, the present assessment did not find many problematic areas but instead provided some insights for improving challenges areas as well as lessons learned for other projects facing the same topics.

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ANNEX I : Ethical questionnaire

i) AUTONOMY

Through what means are the possible risks and/or advantages of participating in research explained to patients? *

- Information sheet
- Consent form
- Interview
- Don't know
- Other

Will the research participants be updated and/or informed of the results/outcomes of the research? If yes, through what means? *

- The participants will not be updated after their participation ends
- They will be updated by email
- They will be contacted by a researcher who will talk to them periodically (by telephone or in person)
- They will be provided with a link to the website where they will be able to learn how the research is progressing
- Don't know
- Other

What is the procedure the participant has to follow in order to abandon the study? *
If there are specific procedures, please put them in the dedicated folder on the sharepoint:

[Selection Criteria and Consent Forms](#)

La tua risposta

Do the participants in the research have the possibility to directly address the clinicians with questions and/or information requests? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Does the algorithm have a system for reporting/explaining its outputs? Will the explanations be understandable also by patients or will the clinicians explain them? *

La tua risposta

How is the accountability of diagnoses and decisions taken with the help of MES-CoBraD guaranteed? Is the clinician always responsible as he/she is when no AI is involved? *

La tua risposta

In your opinion there may exist the risk that the autonomy of clinician's judgment *
is hindered while using the MES-CoBraD system?

La tua risposta

In your opinion there may exist the risk that the autonomy of clinician's judgment *
is hindered while using the MES-CoBraD system?

La tua risposta

What is the expected human-machine interaction between clinicians and the *
mescobrad platform? id est:

- 1. how the clinician and the Expert System will interact and communicate with each other?
- 2. will the system output diagnostic inferences or will it constitute only an information database for the clinician?

La tua risposta

Are there any mechanisms for the patients and/or for the clinicians to contest or *
rectify AI-enabled decisions? How can the patient and/or the clinician access the data on which a certain decision is based?

La tua risposta

Is there the intention to enable MES-CoBraD to take autonomous decisions or will it always be mediated by a human? *

La tua risposta

ii) BENEFICENCE

Please explain how the participation in the research is beneficial to the single participant *

La tua risposta

During the course of a clinical study, previously undiagnosed medical conditions unrelated to the aims of the study are sometimes discovered. These are referred to as 'incidental findings'. Do you have an incidental finding policy? If not, which measures are taken in case a comorbidity or another illness is discovered thanks to the research activities? *

La tua risposta

iii) NON MALEFICENCE

Do you have a risk assessment document? Are there any mitigation strategies for ***** the highlighted risks?

La tua risposta

How are the rights of the vulnerable persons safeguarded? Which additional ***** safeguards are put in place (e.g. in case of children or of mentally impaired persons)?

La tua risposta

Are there established procedures to train the clinicians/researchers who will use ***** the platform?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

How is the risk of depersonalisation of care avoided? Is there the risk that the ***** relationship between the clinician and the patient is modified as an effect of using the MES-CoBraD system?

La tua risposta

How is the security of the system ensured? Indicate whether there is a cybersecurity plan to protect data from external attacks and/or a plan to recover data in case of loss or theft *

La tua risposta

Are there established procedures to request redress? If yes please specify *

La tua risposta

Does a safety case exist and will it be provided to the patient? *

La tua risposta

Is understandability to non-technical personnel (e.g. health personnel) guaranteed? How? *

La tua risposta

Inconclusive evidence: are there defined procedures that grant the patient against ^{*} the possibility of algorithmic error? How will be the effectiveness of MES-CoBraD results proven/verified? (with reference to the following KPI: # of comparisons on accuracy between expert PO analyses offline and with use of online modules within CoBraD ≥ 3)

La tua risposta

iv) JUSTICE

A correct group composition is fundamental to avoid biases, especially when AI ^{*} and machine learning are involved. Please state whether you are reaching the KPIs relative to the group composition stated into the DOA:

- Participant female to male ratio ≈ 1.0 (range 0.8 – 1.2)
- % of participants belonging to an ethnic, socioeconomic, or gender minority $\geq 10\%$
- Congruence of participant socioeconomic background to respective community ≥ 0.7
- Don't know

With reference to the previous question, if you are not reaching one or more KPIs, please state how do you plan to proceed to reach them

La tua risposta

Please state the criteria (inclusion and exclusion) according to which you selected the participants to the research *

La tua risposta

In your opinion does the possibility of misuse and/or abuse of the MES-CoBraD platform exist (e.g. profiling, discrimination, etc)? If yes, what procedures have been enforced to avoid that? *

La tua risposta

Presence of biases: are there any tests to monitor the presence of bias in the execution of the algorithm and are debiasing mechanisms foreseen (with particular reference to historical, representation, measurement, aggregation and evaluation biases)? Could there be racial and/or sex and gender biases involuntarily built into the algorithm? How is it avoided the risk of misdiagnosis or missed diagnosis at scale? *

If there are specific debiasing procedures please put them in the folder on the sharepoint:

[D2.5 Material - Technical Partners](#)

La tua risposta

Do you believe that a system like MES-CoBraD could have negative implications for social justice, inadvertently undermining people's health, or well-being, or increasing disparities in access to social and health service structures? Please explain your answer (either negative or positive) *

La tua risposta

Could MES-CoBraD represent a source of discrimination for clinicians or a barrier (meaning that for some reason, clinicians do not manage to use it)? *

La tua risposta

Could MES-CoBraD worsen the already existing inequalities in access to health care? E.g. favoring certain groups over other ones in access to diagnosis/care? Or "blaming" certain groups of people for their behavior? How do you plan to avoid this possibility? *

La tua risposta
